

Technical performance and overall water smartness and sustainability of alternatives energy production from sludge treatment

Deliverable 2.5

Summary

Bodø Municipality is involved in the EU project B-WaterSmart as one of the living labs. The goal of each living lab is to develop water-smart solutions in collaboration with private businesses and research institutions. This report focuses on improving resource recovery from wastewater in an efficient way given the small scale and decentralized wastewater treatment plant structure in Bodø with six small wastewater treatment plants, which presents a challenge concerning cost-efficient biogas production from sludge according to conventional wisdom. Six alternatives (Alternatives 0-5) were assessed to evaluate the potential of biogas production from different sludge and solid waste streams from Bodø and the surrounding area in Salten. Overall, the results indicate that Alternative 4 will be the preferred solution. This is mainly due to a combination of having valuable products (biogas, bio-oil and biochar) and saving volume and presumably investment costs by using an UASB instead of an anaerobic digester. This is what one would expect based on the comparisons of volume and footprint as well as the energy balance in the technical assessment. However, due to limited data availability, one should take this only as a preliminary conclusion that should be verified considering the uncertainties in the value chain for bio-oil and biochar and the level of accuracy in the technical evaluation.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AD	:	Anaerobic digester
AEL	:	Associated emission level
Anammox	:	Anaerobic ammonium oxidation
BAT	:	Best available technique
BFCOD	:	Biodegradable soluble chemical oxygen demand
BOD ₅	:	Biochemical oxygen demand after 5-day incubation time
CHP	:	Combined heat and power
COD	:	Chemical oxygen demand
DS	:	Dry solid
FBOD ₅	:	Soluble biochemical oxygen demand
FCOD	:	Soluble chemical oxygen demand
FOG	:	Fat, oil, and grease
HRT	:	Hydraulic retention time
IRR	:	Internal rate of return
KOSTRA	:	<i>KOmmune-STat-RApportering</i>
MBBR	:	Moving bed bioreactor
NH ₄ -N	:	Ammonia nitrogen
NFR	:	Norges forskningsråd, The research council of Norway
NPV	:	Net present value
p.e.	:	Person equivalent
PO ₄	:	Soluble/ortho-phosphate
PP	:	Payback period
ROI	:	Return of investment
SDGs	:	Sustainable Development Goals
SCES	:	Symbiotic circular economy solutions
SLR	:	Sludge loading rate
SS	:	Suspended solid
THP	:	Thermal hydrolysis process
Tot-N	:	Total nitrogen
Tot-P	:	Total phosphorus
TS	:	Total solid
UASB	:	Up flow anaerobic sludge blanket
VSS	:	Volatile suspended solid
WS&S	:	Water smartness and sustainability
WWTP	:	Wastewater treatment plant

Executive summary

Bodø Municipality is involved in the EU project B-WaterSmart as one of the living labs together with Venice, Lisbon, East Frisia, Flanders and Alicante. The goal of each living lab is to develop water-smart solutions in collaboration with private businesses and research institutions.

This report focuses on improving resource recovery from wastewater in an efficient way given the small scale and decentralized wastewater treatment plant structure in Bodø with six small wastewater treatment plants, which presents a challenge concerning cost-efficient biogas production from sludge according to conventional wisdom. The study has addressed the potential energy recovery in the form of biogas production from different solid waste/sludge streams of different characteristics, i.e., municipal sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and solid wastes from different sources (e.g., food, aquaculture, and agriculture wastes). The comparison between energy production based on sludge inputs originated solely from Bodø (i.e., decentralized solution) and combining all sludge sources in the surrounding areas (i.e., centralized solution) is also incorporated in the assessment. In addition, the report highlights the results from a feasibility study focusing on the technical aspects of treatment and resource recovery from the digestate and reject water after biogas production.

Six alternatives (Alternatives 0-5) were assessed to evaluate the potential of biogas production from different sludge and solid waste streams from Bodø and the surrounding area in Salten. The technical assessment was extended to compare the water smartness and sustainability of the alternatives using the Water Smartness and Sustainability Index developed in the H2020 project WIDER UPTAKE, which is collaboration with B-Water Smart in the CIRSEAU cluster.

Conclusions from the technical assessment of the alternatives:

- Biogas recovered from digester was calculated for all alternatives, with its net energy production potential through CHP unit. Alternatives 3 and 4 include biogas generated through pyrolysis unit (py-gas). Alternative 4 had the most favourable net energy balance.
- Compost in cold climate countries can require additional energy for heating the compost pile to mesophilic condition during winter, which will affect the energy requirement of this solution. Further, the availability of sufficient agricultural land with crops that allow use of wastewater sludge for soil improvement close to the treatment plant must be assessed to define the viability of Alternatives 0, 1 and 5 which leads to compost product.
- Biopellets, biochar, and bio-oil from Alternatives 2, 3 and 4 are valuable products that can be sold on the market as fertilizer for the first two, or directly reused as fuel for different processes (biopellets or bio-oil). A specific study of the market opportunities is recommended to be carried out to further assess this potential.
- Alternative 3, with pyrolysis of the digestate from the anaerobic digester where biogas is produced has the most power production excess, closely followed by Alternative 4 that uses an UASB for biogas production.
- Alternative 4 with UASB for biogas production is the most compact alternative with lowest footprint compared to other alternatives using conventional anaerobic digestors. Considering the close relation between infrastructure size and cost, Alternative 4 may be the preferred solution from a cost perspective.
- For all alternatives, reject water treatment can be by a traditional end of pipe solution or, alternatively, be with implemented with recovery of struvite fertilizer. For both cases

optimization of the design will be required to ensure compliance with the expected discharge standards.

The assessment of water smartness and sustainability confirms the need for more sludge than available in Bodø municipality and that aiming for other products than compost in addition to biogas is favourable. The results from the assessment show clearly that data availability has been an issue. One should therefore consider this as a preliminary assessment.

Overall, the results indicate that Alternative 4 will be the preferred solution. This is mainly due to a combination of having valuable products (biogas, bio-oil and biochar), and saving volume and presumably investment costs by using an UASB instead of an anaerobic digester. This is what one would expect based on the comparisons of volume and footprint as well as the energy balance in the technical assessment. However, as noted, one should take this only as a preliminary conclusion that should be verified considering the uncertainties in the value chain for bio-oil and biochar and the level of accuracy in the technical evaluation.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background of the case study

Bodø is a city in the Northern Norway with a population of approximately 62 200 inhabitants. The city is aiming to become a low-emission society and adapt to climate change. However, the city is facing several challenges that affect its water resources, including a growing population, increasing anthropogenic pollution, and an untapped efficiency potential.

Bodø Municipality is involved in the EU project B-WaterSmart. The project started in 2020 and will last until 2024. The purpose of the project is to facilitate the development of a water-smart economy and water-smart society. In the project, Bodø is together with Venice, Lisbon, East Frisia, Flanders and Alicante as the so-called living labs, which develop water-smart solutions in collaboration with private businesses and research institutions. Through B-WaterSmart, Bodø Municipality collaborates with the partners in the project in three major topics that often characterize the challenges faced by many small to medium-size cities in the northern regions¹:

- i. Improve resource recovery from wastewater in an efficient way given the small scale, especially concerning biogas production from sludge;
- ii. Improve the handling of wastewater by improved infiltration detection technologies coupled with leak detection (from drinking water pipes) technologies in an integrated system, to reduce energy consumption and improve the management of the wastewater stream;
- iii. Reduce the use of de-icing and anti-slip agents in the city centre to significantly improve air quality and reduce soil & water pollution. The alternative de-icing will use excess heat from biogas utilization for electricity production in combination with heat from seawater.

This report focuses on point i) above addressing the potential energy recovery in the form of biogas production from different solid waste/sludge streams of different characteristics, i.e., municipal sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and solid wastes from different sources (e.g., food, aquaculture, and agriculture wastes). The comparison between energy production based on sludge inputs originated solely from Bodø (i.e., decentralized solution) and combining all sludge sources in the surrounding areas (i.e., centralized solution) is also incorporated in the assessment. In addition, the report highlights the results from a feasibility study focusing on the technical aspects of treatment and resource recovery from the digestate and reject water after biogas production. The alternatives are also evaluated with regards to their 'water smartness' index by means of an assessment framework in collaboration with a similar EU project, Wider Uptake.

1.2 Goal and objectives

The aim of Task 2.2.2 is to perform an initial water smartness assessment of biogas production from different solid waste/sludge streams and resource recovery from the digestate and reject water in Bodø and its surrounding areas. The objectives of the task are as follows:

1. To evaluate the potential of biogas production from different sludge and solid waste streams.

¹ <https://b-watersmart.eu/download/factsheet-living-lab-bodo-norway/>

2. To develop a set of process alternatives for digestate and reject water treatment focusing on the potential by-products with economic value and treated water quality that complies with the effluent discharge regulation.
3. To conduct a technical feasibility study of a set of alternative processes that combine energy production and resource recovery based on literature study, design guidelines, and regulation.
4. Assess how 'water smart' are the alternatives using a holistic water smartness assessment framework.

2 Description of the case study and the assessment method

2.1 Scope of the case study

Referring to the project meeting held in Bodø on March 10th 2023 and the subsequent online meeting on May 10th 2023, a set of biogas production and digestate treatment technologies was agreed upon with Bodø municipality to be included in the case study (Figure 1). The base case was to assess the potential of biogas production exclusively from the municipal wastewater sludge from the city of Bodø. However, an inter-municipal waste management company, IRIS, owned by nine municipalities in the Salten district surrounding Bodø, is already in operation and it is a part of their ambition too to expand their business towards energy recovery and resource recovery from different waste streams they collect from the Salten area. It was therefore decided to assess a centralized solution including sludge from the whole district of Salten that could be more economically viable.

Biogas production by means of thermal hydrolysis process (THP) and mesophilic anaerobic digester (AD) was chosen as process solution. This combination is a common method for biogas production in Norway. In addition, an up flow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) producing biogas from only the liquid fraction of the effluent from the THP was considered because this may provide a potentially more compact process solution (Nilsen, 2023). The biogas production by each alternative was compared in terms of potential heat and electricity generation.

Figure 1 Biogas production from different biosolids treatment considered in the case study

The biogas production by an anaerobic process will in addition to biogas produce a digestate, i.e., a mixture of left over materials from the digestion process. Digestate is often characterized as rich in nutrients and micronutrients necessary for soil conditioning or farming, given that little to no nutrients are lost during anaerobic digestion. Regulation in Norway limits the use of the stabilized sludge directly on agricultural land according to type of crops. Hence, other options, i.e., products from the digestate with economic value may be of interest. Different physio-

chemical technologies for production of different products with potential economic value, i.e., compost, biopellets, and biochar was considered in this study.

The biogas and digestate process will produce reject water of a quality that cannot be discharged directly to the environment. Therefore, alternatives for reject water treatment with the goal of safe discharge of the effluent to the environment were also considered in the analysis. Denitrifying moving bed bioreactor (MBBR) was considered as the main option for biological treatment. As an alternative, a combination of a partly nitrifying MBBR with struvite precipitation and anaerobic ammonium oxidation (Anammox) was also assessed.

Details on the different technologies assigned to the different alternatives are given in Sections 2.2 and 3.2.

2.2 Description of the technology choices

Inclusion of a THP process prior to AD has been proven beneficial by increasing the biodegradability of the solids for the AD process and enabling an increased organic loading rate, thus reducing the required size of the AD. Consequently, a THP process will help increase the biogas production and reduce the downstream requirements for post treatments, e.g., sterilization and drying of the sludge.

AD is a process through which bacteria break down organic matter (e.g., animal manure, wastewater biosolids, and food wastes) in the absence of oxygen (i.e., anaerobic condition). AD for biogas production takes place in a sealed reactor, which is designed and constructed in various shapes and sizes specific to the site and feedstock conditions. The reactor contains complex microbial communities that break down the waste and produce biogas and digestate. UASB has gained attention in recent years for biogas production in which a three-phase separation (i.e., water, sludge mixture, and gas) takes place under high turbulence conditions. This allows for compact and cheaper design in comparison to AD. AD is generally considered well-mixed if more than 90% of the volume of the tank is circulating at a velocity greater than 0.1 m/s. At this velocity, the tank contents are homogeneous, allowing for effective organic material digestion. In contrast, in a UASB the substrate passes through an expanded sludge bed/layer containing a high concentration of biomass and a lesser density sludge layer in which most of the digestion processes take place. Multiple organic materials can be combined in a digester, a practice called co-digestion. Co-digested materials can include manure; food waste (i.e., processing and/or consumer generated materials); crops; crop residues; and fats, oils, and greases (FOG) from restaurant grease traps, and many other sources. Co-digestion can increase biogas production from low-yielding or difficult-to-digest organic waste.

Digestate treatment options can be tailor-made to separate liquid and nutrients from the solid in the digestate. This enables targeted nutrient to be processed further downstream and for the solids to be applied in different manners. The circular economy approach involves the conditioning of bio-residues intended for use as agricultural inputs, e.g., as organic fertilizers. A lot of studies are focused on the development of technologically advanced organic fertilizers. Three environmentally friendly technologies for treating bio-residues, i.e., composting, pelletizing, and pyrolysis were considered in this case study. Compost is arguably still the most frequently used product by farmers as organic fertilizers due to the high quality of the nutrients they provide to plants and other good agronomic properties. Pelletizing is an established technique for further solid digestate that involves a thermal process for drying. Pelletizing reduces the volume of the raw material through compression and simultaneously increases bulk

density and durability of the product. As a result, handling and transportation are facilitated and the required storage volume is minimized. Additionally, the substrate is homogenized, and nutrients are concentrated, which ultimately leads to improved fertilizing and amending properties of the pellets. Treated bio-residues not only provide nutrients to the crops but also improve the physical soil properties, such as the structure, and consequently improve the aeration and water holding capacity. They can also increase biological activity and can be applied as soil amendment or conditioner. Biochar is obtained by pyrolysis of bio-residues, and although it provides reduced quantities of nutrients for crops, it improves their physical, chemical, and biological properties, indirectly affecting their fertility and becoming an innovative and highly promising soil conditioner for sustainable agriculture. Given the low quantity of assimilable nutrients provided by the biochar, but its well-known role as an agronomic enhancer and potentially economic value, biochar has been selected as an alternative product.

The reject water from AD and digestate post treatment would likely be rich in nutrients and organic materials. Such water is unfit to be discharged directly to the environment. For reject water treatment, the focus was put on MBBR in combination with struvite and Anammox process to target organic matter reduction, phosphorus and nitrogen recovery as struvite, and denitrification of the remaining nitrogen with the aim to fulfil the effluent water quality requirements and to recover a product with economic values. The case study also compares the proposed reject water treatment line with the somewhat conventional system i.e., denitrifying MBBR in combination with chemical precipitation to highlight the alternative of an end-of-pipe approach.

Mark that Task 2.2.2 did not include/discuss optimization of the process lines chosen for each alternative. Hence, variations in the input material's quality and quantity, performance of the unit operation and processes, and the quality of the end products were excluded from the analysis. The reader can refer to Section 3.1 for further details on the assumptions and boundaries of the case study.

2.3 Alternatives considered in the case study Bodø

Table 1 depicts the six alternatives of sludge-to-energy production that have been assessed in the case study. The table gives an overview of technology assigned to each alternative, the input raw sludge considered for the biosolid treatment, and the products including their potential marketed form.

A short summary of each alternative is presented below:

- Alt.0 : This is the base case alternative described for Bodø in which only municipal sludge from Bodø area is considered (i.e., decentralized solution). The technology for sludge treatment includes a THP in combination with an AD for biogas production, and the stabilized biosolid is further processed as compost. The reject water treatment involves a denitrifying MBBR process.
- Alt.1 : This is an alternative for a centralized solution in which the sludge treatment receives different sludge streams as the input for the process. The technology for sludge treatment includes a THP in combination with an AD for biogas production. Garden waste is added prior to composting together with the biosolid from the sludge treatment. The reject water treatment involves an MBBR process for organic carbon reduction, phosphorus recovery as struvite, and denitrification by

means of an anammox process. Alternatively, a denitrifying MBBR is also assessed as a means of comparison with the MBBR-struvite-anammox line.

Table 1 Summary of the alternatives

Alt.	Technology		Input					Output	Possible marketed output
	Sludge	Reject water	Bode sludge	Salten sludge	Food waste	Garden waste	Fish sludge		
Alt.0	THP + AD + Composting	MBBR	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	biogas, compost	Heat, electricity, compost
Alt.1	THP + AD + Composting	MBBR	YES	YES	YES	YES (in composting)	YES	biogas, compost, struvite	Heat, electricity, compost, struvite
		MBBR + Struvite + Anammox							
Alt.2	THP + AD + Pelletizing	MBBR + Struvite + Anammox	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	biogas, biopellet, struvite	Heat, electricity, biopellet, struvite
Alt.3	THP + AD + Pyrolysis	MBBR + Struvite + Anammox	YES	YES	YES	YES (in pyrolysis)	YES	biogas, biochar, struvite	Heat, electricity, biochar, struvite
Alt.4	THP + UASB + Pyrolysis	MBBR + Struvite + Anammox	YES	YES	YES	YES (in pyrolysis)	YES	biogas, biochar, struvite	Heat, electricity, biochar, struvite
Alt.5	2 lines (THP + AD + Composting)	MBBR + Struvite + Anammox	YES	YES	YES (separated)	YES (in composting)	YES	biogas, compost, struvite	Heat, electricity, compost, struvite

Alt.2 : This is an alternative for a centralized solution in which the sludge treatment receives different sludge streams as the input for the process except for garden waste. The technology for sludge treatment includes a THP in combination with an AD for biogas production. Biopellet production via thermal pelletizing of the biosolid is considered. The reject water treatment involves an MBBR process for organic carbon reduction, phosphorus recovery as struvite, and denitrification by means of an anammox process.

Alt.3 This is an alternative for a centralized solution in which the sludge treatment receives different sludge streams as the input for the process. The technology for sludge treatment includes a THP in combination with an AD for biogas production. Garden waste is added prior to pyrolysis together with the biosolid from the sludge treatment. The end product from this process is in the form of biochar. The reject water treatment involves an MBBR process for organic carbon reduction, phosphorus recovery as struvite, and denitrification by means of an anammox process.

Alt.4 This is an alternative for a centralized solution in which the sludge treatment receives different sludge streams as the input for the process. The technology for sludge treatment includes a THP in combination with a UASB for biogas production. Garden waste is added prior to pyrolysis together with the biosolid from the sludge treatment. The end product from this process is in the form of biochar. The reject water treatment involves an MBBR process for organic carbon

reduction, phosphorus recovery as struvite, and denitrification by means of an anammox process.

- Alt.5 This is an alternative for a centralized solution in which the sludge treatment receives different sludge streams as the input for the process. The technology for sludge treatment includes a THP in combination with an AD for biogas production. Note that the food waste is treated separately to address restriction by the regulation, and the garden waste is added prior to composting together with the biosolid from the sludge treatment. The reject water treatment involves an MBBR process for organic carbon reduction, phosphorus recovery as struvite, and denitrification by means of an anammox process.

3 Assessment method

3.1 Assumptions / study boundaries

Several assumptions and constraints include:

- Calculations were done according to Bodø population in 2023, with 62 200 persons equivalent (p.e.) and sludges amount inputs from 2022².
- The present study did not consider other future scenarios of increased population and higher sludge volumes. Moreover, the input materials quality was assumed constant and was not under seasonal influence.
- Energy requirements for transport of sludge/flow from a process step to another are not included. Energy calculation was limited to the energy requirement and recovery from the process reaction itself.
- Effluent standards: The reject water treatment was designed to comply with the Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (c.q., Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2018/1147) (EU Commission, 2018) and compared with the Council Directive 91/271/EEC of 21 May 1991 concerning urban waste-water treatment (c.q., Revision of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive In “A European Green Deal”) (Halleux, 2024).

Data from primary and secondary sources were collected for the case study. The available primary data includes only the quantity of the raw material flows. Data on the characteristics of these raw materials were unavailable and, hence, the analysis was reliant on the data from the literature.

3.1.1 Quantity of raw materials

The data on quantity of the raw materials, i.e., different sludge and waste inputs in Table 2 were taken from 2022 data and agreed upon with Bodø Municipality and IRIS to serve as the baseline for analysis. Total amount of municipal sludge and septic sludge were 3000 tons and 4300 tons, respectively, in which 45% of the former and 80% of the latter was associated to Bodø municipality. Food waste (9000 tons) and sludge from fisheries (200 tons) were also included in the treatment process calculation of Salten sludge. Table 1 specifies the sludge/waste types included in the different alternatives considered. The information of total solid content from municipal and septic sludge were taken from the data provided by IRIS, whereas the data for food (Selvam et al., 2021), garden (Mk et al., 2013), and fish sludge (Estevez et al., 2022) were collected from the literature.

Table 2 Raw material input for the process

Type of sludge/waste	Amount [Ton/year]	Total solid content [%]	Description
Municipal sludge	~3000	24	45% from Bodø Municipality
Septic sludge	~4300	0.7	80% from Bodø Municipality
Food waste	~9000	23	
Garden waste	~6000	45	
Fish sludge	~200	8.2	

² <https://bodo.kommune.no/vei-vann-og-avlop/vann-og-avlop/forskrifter-normer-og-retningslinjer/hovedplan-avlop-2019-2026/>

3.1.2 Quality/characteristics of raw materials

In order to allow the analysis of material balance for each alternative, it was necessary to assume the initial sludge/waste characteristics. Table 3 shows the characteristics of each sludge/waste input considered in the mass-balance analysis.

Table 3 Characteristics of different sludge/waste streams

Parameter	Unit	Fish sludge	Sewage sludge	Septic sludge	Food waste	Garden waste
Quantity	(m ³ /d)	0.5	8.2	11.8	24.7	16.4
TS	%	8.2	24	0.7	23.0	45.0
SS	kg/d	44.9	1942.4	82.5	5671.2	-
COD	kg/d	36.7	2736.9	116.2	6435.6	-
FCOD	kg/d	13.6	1.5	0.1	2362.2	-
BFCOD	kg/d	13.3	1.2	0.1	2361.9	-
BOD ₅	kg/d	14.5	1080.3	45.9	2540.4	-
FBOD ₅	kg/d	5.4	0.6	0.0	932.4	-
Tot-N	kg/d	1.5	108.6	4.6	111.9	-
NH ₄ -N	kg/d	1.0	0.2	0.0	10.6	-
Tot-P	kg/d	1.8	14.7	0.6	44.9	-
PO ₄ -P	kg/d	0.1	0.0	0.0	13.5	-

The following points highlight important considerations for the values in Table 3:

- 1) The values for municipal sewage sludge parameters were extracted from the Research Council (Norges forskningsråd - NFR) project RECOVER (2015-2020). The values were based on the key figures reported in KOSTRA (*KOmmune-STat-RApportering*) by municipalities and county-municipals in Norway to the Statistics Norway³. The values were based on real wastewater characteristics data from 1987-2015. The reported values in KOSTRA include suspended solid (SS), chemical oxygen demand (COD), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD₅), total and ammonium nitrogen (TOT-N and NH₄-N, respectively), total and ortho-phosphate (TOT-P and PO₄-P, respectively).
- 2) KOSTRA does not provide some of the specific values in Table 3, e.g., soluble chemical oxygen demand (FCOD), biodegradable soluble COD (BFCOD), and soluble biochemical oxygen demand (FBOD₅). Given that the raw material is in the form of dewatered sludge with 24% TS on average, the amount of FCOD must be low, i.e., particulate COD is predominant. The amount of FCOD in the municipal sludge was taken from the typical value of soluble COD in municipal wastewater in Norway (Ødegaard, H., 1992), and then the value of FCOD in the municipal sludge was calculated from the ratio of the average %TS in the sludge and the wastewater data.
- 3) The value of biodegradable soluble COD (BFCOD) was estimated as the difference between FCOD value estimated in bullet 2) and the typical 'hard' COD values (i.e., non-biodegradable soluble COD) found in various wastewater related projects that lies typically around ~25-35 mg COD/L (Ivanovic and Leiknes, 2008; Fanta et al., 2024).

³ <https://www.ssb.no/offentlig-sektor/kostra/statistikk/kostra-kommune-stat-rapportering/om-kostra>

- 4) The concentration of soluble BOD₅ (FBOD₅) was estimated from the ratio of BOD₅ and COD values reported in KOSTRA multiplied by the FCOD value estimated in bullet 3).
- 5) For all sludge/waste inputs, the content of volatile suspended solid (VSS) is assumed to be 80% of SS.
- 6) All values for septic sludge parameters were estimated from those of the sewage sludge by taking into account the ratio of %TS (total solid) and quantity of the two sludge streams.
- 7) Characterization parameters suspended solid (SS), chemical oxygen demand (COD), total nitrogen (TOT-N), and total phosphorus (TOT-P) of the fish sludge were taken from the literature (Estevez et al., 2022) and were considered to be similar to that of fish smolt sludge. The concentrations of other parameters (FCOD, BFCOD, FBOD₅) were estimated from the values for municipal sludge by taking into account the ratio of %TS and amount of the two sludge streams.
- 8) Food waste parameters were considered to be the same as the raw food waste reported in Ismail et al. (2022) and Selvam et al. (2021).
- 9) Garden waste dry-solid fraction was taken from the values reported by Mk et al., (2013).

3.2 Treatment and resource recovery concepts

3.2.1 Biogas production and digestate post-treatment

Figure 2 depicts a more detailed flow scheme of the alternatives considered in this case study. As seen in the figure, the receiving end of the waste/sludge inputs (Box 1 in the figure) is similar for all alternatives. The goal of this step is to produce a sludge with appropriate characteristics, especially solid content (%TS) for the biogas production unit. Given that the sludge/waste inputs exhibit different %TS and the fact that the installation will receive the raw material input intermittently, each sludge/waste input is given a dedicated storage unit to balance the variations. As seen in Table 2, the septic sludge has the lowest solid content and requires a pre-dewatering unit prior to mixing with the sewage sludge. A separate mixing unit is provided for the food waste and fish sludge and the %TS content of these sludges is adjusted by mixing it with the treated reject water. The targeted %TS content for THP is set to 16-18% following the information provided by CAMBI (Nilsen, 2016).

Box 2 in Figure 2 presents (Alternatives 0/1, 2, and 3) biogas production unit using a mesophilic anaerobic digester (AD) and the subsequent water-solid separation unit for the AD digestate. A series of dewatering units consisting of a gravity thickener and a centrifuge is necessary to make sure that the AD digestate has the correct %TS content for the digestate's solid post-treatment in Box 3. As seen in Box 3, the alternatives for solid post-treatment include composting, pelletizing, pyrolysis for Alternatives 0/1, 2, and 3, respectively. Mark that the garden waste is considered only for alternatives 1 and 3 with a dedicated shredding unit as the pretreatment for this type of waste. For Alternative 3, a combined heat-electricity (CHP) unit is included for the pyrolysis gases and combined with the biogas yield from AD.

Box 4 shows the flow scheme of biogas and digestate post-treatment for Alternative 4. Biogas production by means of an up flow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) is considered. It is deemed necessary to include an extra solid-liquid separation prior to UASB following the design guideline. The digestate post-treatment is similar to Alternative 3, aiming for pyrolysis of the solid fraction, and combining the pyrolysis gases and biogas yield from AD in a dedicated combine heat-electricity (CHP) unit.

3.2.2 Reject water treatment

Figure 3 depicts the two options for reject water treatment considered in the case study. For the purpose of the case study, treatment of the reject water from the pre-dewatering unit of the septic sludge, gravity thickener, and centrifuge were assessed with regards to two EU directives that were considered relevant: Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (c.q., Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2018/1147) (EU Commission, 2018) and Council Directive 91/271/EEC of 21 May 1991 concerning urban waste-water treatment (c.q., Revision of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive In “A European Green Deal”) (Halleux, 2024), instead of the discharge permit assigned for IRIS by the local government. This was to ensure that the future new requirements set by the incoming new regulations would be fulfilled.

Option A represents the more 'end-of-pipe' technology in which the focus is to remove as technologically feasible as possible the pollutants in the wastewater. This alternative includes a denitrifying moving bed bioreactor (MBBR) designed to remove the organic carbon and nitrogen/nitrogenous compounds followed by chemical precipitation to remove the remaining phosphorus and ensure efficient separation of suspended solids. The case study excludes the discussion of post-treatment of the chemical sludge from this treatment alternative.

Option B is developed to target recovery of the nutrients (P and N) in the form of struvite. Struvite has a potential economic value if it can be resold as slow-releasing fertilizer. Hence, in this alternative the MBBR merely targets removal of organic carbon. A fraction of the nitrogenous compounds (i.e., ammonium nitrogen) contributes to the struvite production, and hence the anammox process downstream functions as a polishing step for the remaining nitrogenous compounds.

A technical performance comparison between Alternatives A and B was done for Alternative 1 (see Table 1) to highlight the differences between these two reject water treatment alternatives.

Figure 2 Alternatives for biogas production from different biosolids treatments considered in the case study

Figure 3 Reject water treatment options considered in the case study

3.3 Design considerations of the unit operations and processes

3.3.1 Storage unit

Dedicated storage/buffer tanks were included in the analysis with the function to store the different types of sludges arriving intermittently at the treatment plant prior to entering the treatment process. A hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 24 hours was considered for all storage tanks. Details on how the storage tanks should be operated e.g., filling method by conveyor belt, screw pump, or others, were not considered in the analysis.

3.3.2 Dewatering unit

The dewatering unit in the case study was composed of a gravity thickener followed by a centrifuge to enable effective separation of the solid/liquid content. Dimensioning of the gravity thickener followed the guideline in Norsk Vann report (Johannessen et al., 2020), assuming 85% of solid capture and without chemicals addition. A centrifuge was considered to further dewater the settled sludge from the gravity thickener up to 20% SS content. It was assumed that the centrifuge would perform a solid capture efficiency up to 95% SS based on the literature value. The particulate fractions of COD, Tot-P, Tot-N and BOD₅ were also assumed to follow the SS removal efficiency. A collection system for the reject waters from the gravity thickener and centrifuge was included in the analysis of the reject water treatment downstream. Details of the design parameters adopted in the evaluation are described in Table 4 (Johannessen et al., 2020).

Table 4 Principal design criteria for dewatering unit

Gravity thickener	Surface loading rate	0.75	m/hour
	Sludge loading rate	35	kg SS/m ² /d
	Suspended solids (SS) removal	85	%
	Sludge concentration after pre-dewatering	8	%
	Specific energy consumption	10	kWh/ton TS
Centrifuge	Suspended solids (SS) removal	95	%
	Specific energy consumption	100	kWh/ton TS
	Sludge concentration after pre-dewatering	20	%

3.3 Sludge mixing unit

A mechanical mixing unit was included in the technical assessment to mix the sludge inputs with different solid contents (i.e., the septic and municipal sludges). In order to simplify the design calculation, given that the mechanical mixing unit should only be a physical unit operation that would not pose any changes in the sludge's bio-chemical characteristics, the design values in Table 5 were adopted⁴.

Table 5 Principal design criteria for sludge mixing unit

Type	Rotor diameter (mm)	Length (m)	Motor power (kW)	Max throughput (m ³ /h)
A	150	1.0-2.1	1.1	2
B	240	1.5-3.0	2.2	7
C	350	2.2-3.7	4.0	15
D	500	3.3-5.1	7.5	24

⁴ <https://sodimate.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/SODIMATE-MBV-EN.pdf>

3.3.4 Thermal hydrolysis process (THP)

Thermal hydrolysis process (THP) exposes pre-dewater sludge to high temperature and pressure, using steam. The process technology developed by Cambi (Sahu et al., 2022) that was considered in this case study includes three tank reactors as presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Schematic drawing of Cambi's THP unit

The first tank is a pulper which receives the feedstock and where the sludge is preheated before it goes to the reactor, which is the heart of the reaction process at high temperature and high pressure. In the reactor, pathogens are killed, and the sludge is sterilized. Then in the flash tank where pressure and temperature drops, organic matter is partly destroyed, which further enables increased production of energy from the downstream anaerobic digestion (AD) process, it reduces the required digester volume, and decreases the volume of biosolids to be handled or transported at the end of the chain, while improving its quality. THP has been dimensioned according to the information from CAMBI provided for the RECOVER project (Nilsen, 2016) and Han et al. (2017), with the main design parameters listed in Table 6.

Table 6 Principal design criteria for THP unit

Sludge storage	HRT	24	hours
Heating and hydrolysis	Temperature	170	°C
	Pressure	7	bar
	HRT	0.50	hours
	Sludge concentration	10	%
	Degradation of VSS	0	%
Transformation of sludge after THP	SS destruction	~46	%
	Tot-N conversion	~13	%
	Tot-P conversion	~28	%
Energy requirement	Specific energy consumption	0.1	kWh/kg SS

It was assumed that 20% of the inlet SS consists of inorganic materials (e.g., silt, clay) that would not undergo destruction during the thermal hydrolysis process according to Hamilton and Zhang (2016). The remaining 80% of the inlet SS was assumed to be of organic in nature and would undergo conversion following the factor specified in Table 6, hence the outlet SS can be evaluated using Eq. 1:

$$SS_{out} = 20\% \cdot SS_{in} + (1 - \%SS \text{ destruction}) \cdot 80\% \cdot SS_{in} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

In which,

- SS_{in} : Inlet suspended solid [mg/L]
 SS_{out} : Outlet suspended solid [mg/L]

Referring to the characteristics of the raw materials in Table 3 Characteristics of different sludge/waste streams

, the amount of intermediate nitrogenous and phosphorus compounds at the inlet of THP can be evaluated as the difference between the total nitrogenous and phosphorus (Tot-N and Tot-P) and the NH_4-N and PO_4-P , respectively. A fraction of Tot-N and Tot-P is solubilized/converted to NH_4-N and PO_4-P , respectively, in the THP reactor according to the conversion percentages reported by Han et al. (2017) in Table 6. While Tot-N and Tot-P values will remain the same (i.e., $Tot-N_{in}/Tot-P_{in} = Tot-N_{out}/Tot-P_{out}$), the values of NH_4-N and PO_4-P at the outlet will increase to the extent represented by Eq. 2.

$$X_{out} = X_{in} + \%X \text{ conversion} \cdot (TotX_{in} - X_{in}) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

In which,

- X_{in} : NH_4-N or PO_4-P at the inlet [mg/L]
 X_{out} : NH_4-N or PO_4-P at the outlet [mg/L]
 $TOTX_{in}$: Tot-N or Tot-P at the inlet [mg/L]

Energy requirement for the THP was calculated based on the steam consumption (185 kg of steam/kg SS) and the specific energy requirement (0.1 kWh/kg SS) (Ringoot et al., 2012).

3.3.5 Heat exchanger unit

A spiral heat exchanger unit is a process where two flows are put in contact with each other but physically separated, allowing exchange of heat (energy) from the hot flow to the cold one without any exchange of matter. In the evaluation, the input sludge is preheated to 88 °C before entering the THP unit thanks to a spiral heat exchanger unit placed at the outlet of the THP, where cold raw sludge (10 °C) absorbs excess heat from hydrolysed sludge (170 °C) which has to be cooled down to 40 °C for further mesophilic treatment (AD). Heat exchanger efficiency was set at 60% according to Lines (2024).

3.3.6 Anaerobic digester (AD)

Anaerobic digestion is a biological process where bacteria break down biodegradable matter in the absence of oxygen to produce biogas and a digestate containing solid and liquid compounds remaining after the digestion process. This process degrades volatile suspended solid (VSS) in a sealed reactor. Table 7 presents the design criteria of the anaerobic digester used in this study. A mesophilic AD was considered and the design calculation was done based on VSS mass-balance over the digester (Johannessen et al., 2020).

Table 7 Principal design criteria for anaerobic digester

Anaerobic digester main parameters	Sludge concentration from THP	10	%
	HRT	12	days
	Sludge loading rate	6	kg VSS/m ³ /day
	VSS/SS ratio	80	%
	VSS degradation	60	%
Biogas production	$Y_{biogas/VSS-degraded}$	0.90	Nm ³ /kg VSS

The design AD reactor volume was the largest of the volumes calculated from the HRT and the sludge loading rate. A 60% VSS degradation and 0.90 Nm³/kg VSS biogas yield were conservative values adopted in the evaluation based on Cambi's experience (Nilsen, 2016) and the Norsk Vann report no. 256 (Johannessen et al., 2020). Hence, biogas production can be calculated using Eq. 3.

$$Q_{biogas} = VSS_{in} * \%VSS \text{ degradation} * Y_{biogas/VSS \text{ degraded}} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

In which,

- VSS_{in} : VSS concentration at the inlet [kg/day]
 $Y_{biogas/VSS \text{ degraded}}$: Biogas yield factor [Nm³/kg VSS]
 Q_{biogas} : Biogas production [Nm³/day]

In addition, it was necessary to calculate the elemental balance for the carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, and nitrogen at the outlet of AD to evaluate the digestate characteristics. Hence, it was necessary to assume the elemental composition of the bulk organic materials fed to the AD process. Table 8 shows the values considered in the case study from Degremont (1991).

Table 8 Elemental composition of the organic materials in AD process

Sludge type	%C	%H	%O	%N
Fresh sludge	56-62	7.9-8.7	26.5-29	3.5-6.8
Digested sludge	53-59	7.2-8.5	28-31	3.0-7.0

Upon choosing the element percentages, the stoichiometric elemental mass balance and the biomass yield could then be evaluated. The detailed formulas to assess how much of each element is degraded in AD is given in APPENDIX A – Elemental balance for biogas production (Moscoviz and Jimenez, 2021). The calculated values for each element are shown in Table 9.

Table 9 Stoichiometric mass balance

Biomass yield	Biomass yield	0.15	g COD/g COD _{consumed}
	H ₂ O (a)	0.39	
	CH ₄ (b)	0.51	
	CO ₂ (c)	0.30	
	NH ₄ ⁺ and HCO ₃ ⁻ (d)	0.02	
	CH _{1.8} O _{0.5} N _{0.2} (e)	0.17	

3.3.7 Up flow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB)

UASB reactor is a process where wastewater flows through a granular sludge bed, leading to phase separation. Treated wastewater exits from the top and sludge will accumulate in the bottom of the reactor. Biogas is produced during the process as anaerobic bacteria break down organic matter, enabling biogas production. In this study a UASB was used as an alternative to a conventional AD to treat the liquid fraction after the THP. Eventhough the solid contents deemed technically feasible for UASB application in the literature were found between 0.3-65 kg/m³ (Karadag et al., 2015), the inclusion of a centrifuge in front of UASB was thought necessary to reduce the solid content in the UASB reactor.

The design of UASB typically involves degradation of COD instead of VSS (Eq. 4) as in the case of AD. Table 10 shows the design criteria for the design valuation of the UASB unit adopted in this case study (Reino et al., 2018).

$$Q_{biogas} = COD_{in} * \%COD\ degradation * Y_{biogas/COD\ degraded} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

In which,

- COD_{in} : COD concentration at the inlet [kg/day]
 $Y_{biogas/COD\ degraded}$: Biogas yield factor [Nm³/kg VSS]
 Q_{biogas} : Biogas production [Nm³/day]

Table 10 Principal design criteria for UASB

UASB main parameters	Selected inlet sludge concentration	~9	kg SS/m ³
	Fraction of solids	1	%
	Hydraulic retention time HRT	10	hours
	Sludge loading rate (SLR)	10	kg COD/m ³ /d
	Upflow velocity	0.5-1	m/h
	COD degradation rate	90	%
Biogas production	$Y_{biogas/COD-degraded}$	0.33	Nm ³ /kg COD

The selected inlet sludge concentration was the calculated result from the previous step prior to UASB. The design UASB reactor volume was the largest between the volumes calculated from the HRT and the sludge loading rate. Upon deciding the volume of the reactor, the required height was determined by satisfying the up-flow velocity, a value that is necessary to keep the sludge afloat inside the reactor.

As in the case of AD, it was necessary to evaluate the elemental mass balance at the outlet of UASB. The approach explained in Section 3.3.6 (Table 8 and Table 9) was followed.

3.3.8 Moving bed bioreactor (MBBR)

In MBBR-based processes, the biomass grows on plastic media (i.e., biofilm carriers) that are kept suspended in the reactor by means of aeration or mechanical mixing. The biofilm carriers are prevented from leaving the reactor together with the water by a sieve on the outlet of the reactor. When MBBR is used for aerobic biodegradation of organic matter or ammonium, the carriers are suspended and mixed in the reactor through aeration, which is necessary for the biological processes. In contrast, if MBBR is used for anoxic processes (i.e., for the biological breakdown of nitrite and nitrate or denitrification) or for anaerobic processes, the media are kept suspended and mixed in the reactor through mechanical stirring. In the treatment of municipal wastewater, pre-treatment through a grit chamber is included, as well as particle separation through fine screening, pre-sedimentation, or sedimentation. Table 11 summarizes the design criteria for MBBR used in the case study (Johannessen et al., 2020).

Table 11 Principal design criteria for MBBR reactor

Loading rate	BOD ₅ load	5	g BOD ₅ /m ² /d
	Ammonium load	0.5	g NH ₄ -N/m ² /d
	Nitrate load	1.5	g NO ₃ -N/m ² /d

Sizing	Filling ratio	40-60	%
	Specific carrier surface area	500	m ² /m ³
	Specific surface area	300	m ² /m ³
	Reactor depth	7	m
Aeration	Clean water O ₂ saturation concentration at 20°C	9.1	mg O ₂ /L
	Temperature of feed water	15	°C
	Specific oxygen transfer capacity	6.0-6.5	g O ₂ /Nm ³ air/m (10 °C, 1 atm)
	Specific Air supply per reactor area	10-15	m ³ /m ² /h
Expected effluent concentration	BOD ₅	15	mg/L
	NH ₄ -N	3	mg/L
	NO ₃ -N	3	mg/L
COD degradation	Assumed yield factor, Y _{COB}	0.5	
Energy requirement	BOD ₅ removal	0.06-0.09	kWh/m ³
	BOD ₅ and denitrification	0.2-0.3	kWh/m ³

Eq. 5 through Eq. 8 are the governing equations for the design of MBBR. The oxygen demand was calculated following Eq. 5. It was assumed that the MBBR would use Kaldnes K1 media and, thus, the technical data (specific carrier surface area, filling ratio) were included in the table. Different loading rates for MBBR design can be applied depending on the oxygen demand that the process requires. As illustrated previously in Figure 3, the case study considered two reject water options: denitrifying MBBR with chemical addition (Option A) and the MBBR-struvite-Annamox line (Option B). Thus, the oxygen demands for these two options were different and, consequently, the loading rates in Table 11 were used accordingly depending on the treatment goal of each option.

$$O_{2\text{demand}} = O_{2\text{demand-BOD}_5} + O_{2\text{demand-NH}_4\text{-N}} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

$$O_{2\text{transfer}} = \frac{f_d \cdot C_{s,20}}{(f_d \cdot C_{m,T} - C_r) \cdot \theta^{(T-20)}} \cdot O_{2\text{demand}} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$Q_{\text{air}} = \frac{O_{2\text{transfer}} \cdot 1000}{SOTC \cdot h_d} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

$$SS_{\text{out}} = SS_{\text{in}} + \Delta BOD_5 + 0.125 \cdot \Delta NH_4 \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

In which,

- $O_{2\text{demand-BOD}_5}$: Oxygen demand for BOD₅ oxidation [=1 kg O₂/kg BOD₅]
- $O_{2\text{demand-NH}_4\text{-N}}$: Oxygen demand for NH₄-N oxidation [=4.3 kg O₂/kg BOD₅]
- $O_{2\text{demand}}$: Total oxygen demand [kg]
- f_d : Depth factor = 1+ $h_d/20.7$ [unitless]
- h_d : Aeration depth [m]
- $C_{s,20}$: Oxygen saturation concentration at 20°C [=9.1 gO₂/m³]
- $C_{m,T}$: Oxygen saturation concentration at actual temperature [gO₂/m³]
- C_r : Oxygen concentration in the reactor [gO₂/m³]
- θ : Temperature correction factor [=1.024]
- T : Actual temperature

$SOTC$:	Specific oxygen transfer capacity, carrier-shape dependent [~6.5 gO ₂ /Nm ³ .m for K1 media]
Q_{air}	:	Air pumping demand [m ³ /h]
SS_{in}	:	Suspended solid concentration at the inlet of MBBR [mg/L]
ΔBOD_5	:	BOD ₅ removed i.e., $BOD_{5,in} - BOD_{5,out}$ [mg/L]
ΔNH_4	:	Ammonium removed i.e., $NH_{4,in} - NH_{4,out}$ [mg/L]
SS_{out}	:	Suspended solid concentration at the outlet of MBBR [mg/L]

It was assumed that the effluent concentrations follow those of the design guideline, i.e., 15 mg BOD₅/L, 3 mg NH₄-N, and 3 mg/L NO₃-N (Johannessen et al., 2020). The requirement for air pumping could then be iterated to satisfy the amount of oxygen needed for the biological processes and a good mixing condition in the reactor.

The calculation of energy requirement for MBBR was taken from the design guideline (Johannessen et al., 2020), with typical values of 0.2 – 0.3 kWh/m³ of total energy consumption (including stirring, aeration, and return pumping) in the case of nitrogen removal, and 0.06 – 0.09 kWh/m³ in the case of only carbon removal.

3.3.9 Struvite formation

The Struvite process is a chemical nutrient recovery method from wastewater through removal of ammonia and phosphorous as struvite crystal (MgNH₄PO₄·6H₂O). Many raw materials recoverable from wastewater treatment can potentially become component materials in the recent Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 (Huygens et al., 2019). Consequently, the simultaneous recovery of nitrogen and phosphorus from wastewater as struvite has gained great interest in recent years. Struvite process can produce a relatively pure phosphorus and nitrogen rich solids fraction with only trace amounts of impurities. Indeed, unlike other precipitation processes that exploit coagulant/flocculant agents, struvite is formed as a mineral salt that can be easily recovered by sedimentation (Siciliano et al., 2020). Therefore, the formation of voluminous flocculant sludge, containing great quantities of unwanted compounds that requires post-treatment, can be sidestepped.

The stoichiometric reaction of the struvite formation (Eq. 9) happens under certain conditions presented in Table 12 (Siciliano et al., 2020). Sea water can be used as a sustainable, natural source for magnesium (Shaddel et al., 2020). The required molar ratio of Mg:P is ranging between 1.0 and 1.6 (Achilleos et al., 2022). Struvite is an efficient process with an expected phosphorous removal up to ~99% (Siciliano et al., 2020). However, the struvite formation is reportedly affected by COD (Xie et al., 2022) and can be inhibited if COD concentration rises above 200 mg/L (Yang et al., 2019). The typical energy consumption for the struvite process was taken from the literature (Ghimire et al., 2021).

Table 12 Principal design criteria for struvite process

Assumptions for process condition	Typical Mg conc. in seawater	~1300	mg/L
	% removal COD	~5	%
	% removal P	99	%
	Optimum Mg:P ratio	1.5	Between 1-1.6
Reactor design	pH	9	Between 8-10.5

	HRT	2	hours
Energy requirement	Specific energy consumption	0.012-0.033	kWh/m ³

3.3.10 Anaerobic ammonium oxidation (Anammox)

Anaerobic ammonium oxidation (anammox) is a biological process used to remove nitrogen and nitrite from wastewater without the need for oxygen. The combined processes of partial nitrification and Anammox are often called deammonification, independently of whether the process is run in a single or in two separate steps. There are already several commercial anammox technologies on the market mostly used for reject water treatment. Arguably, the widely chosen and already applied in several full-scale systems are, among others, DEMON⁵, SHARON-Anammox, ANITA-Mox⁶ and DeAmmon⁷.

The anammox process is carried out at mesophilic temperature by anammox bacteria, crosscutting the nitrogen cycle and offering an efficient nitrogen removal alternative to conventional nitrogen removal process. Removal rate of reportedly up to 90% (Driessen et al., 2012) can be attained in short time, with a typical HRT of 10h and 24h for nitrification and anammox, respectively (Ma et al., 2019). Oxygen/aeration is only needed for the partial nitrification step ($NH_4 \rightarrow NO_2^-$) in which nitrite acts as the oxidizer in the reaction in Eq. 10. The typical energy consumption for the anammox process was taken from the literature (Ghimire et al., 2021). Principal design criteria for the anammox reactor are detailed in Table 13.

Table 13 Principal design criteria for anammox process

Partial nitrification reactor	% partial nitrification (NO_2^-)	50	%
	HRT	10	hour
	Clean water O_2 saturation concentration at 20°C	9.1	mg O_2 /L
	Temperature of feed water	15	°C
	Clean water O_2 saturation concentration at actual temperature	10	mg O_2 /L
	Oxygen content in reactor	0	mg/L
	Specific oxygen transfer capacity	6.5	g O_2 /Nm ³ air/m (10 °C, 1 atm)
Anammox reactor	Nitrogen volumetric loading rate	2.3	kg NH_4 -N/m ³ /d
	Nitrogen removal rate	90	%
	Operating temperature	35	°C
	HRT	24	hour
Energy requirement	Specific energy consumption	0.02-0.09	kWh/m ³

3.3.11 Sedimentation tank

Sedimentation tanks based on lamella settler technology were considered in the case study. The use of lamella settlers was considered advantageous to reduce the footprint of the sedimentation tank significantly and to improve the solid separation efficiency.

⁵ <https://wawa-tech.com/en/technologies/demon/>

⁶ <https://www.veoliawatertechnologies.com/en/solutions/technologies/anita-mox>

⁷ https://purac.se/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Bekkelaget_CS_SE_Hi-ok.pdf

Table 14 summarizes the design criteria adopted in the design calculation taken from Johannessen et al. (2020) and Degremont (1991). In cases where chemical addition was deemed necessary (i.e., reject water treatment Option A), then the sludge coefficient was applied to calculate the chemical sludge production (Ødegaard, 2012). A somewhat conservative 85% removal efficiency was chosen for the analysis.

Table 14 Principal design criteria for settling tank

Tank design	Surface loading	0.4-0.6 0.6-1.0	m ³ /m ² /h (no chemical addition) m ³ /m ² /h (with chemical addition)
	Depth	≥3.0	m
Lamella plate	Degree of inclination	60	°
	Height	1	m
	Space between plates	5	cm
Chemical use	Sludge coefficient	3-6	g SS/g chemical
Separation efficiency	Removal efficiency	80-95	%
	Sludge concentration	1-2	%
Energy requirement	Specific energy consumption	0.005	kWh/m ³

3.3.12 Centrifuge

In order to increase the solid concentration even higher for the downstream solid treatment alternatives (i.e., biopellet, pyrolysis, or composting), a centrifuge was included in the technical evaluation such that the dewatered/settled sludge from the thickener or the settling tank units could fulfil the ideal solid content for the downstream solid processing. Table 15 recaps the design criteria for centrifuge (Johannessen et al., 2020). A particle removal efficiency of 95% was used in the calculation.

Table 15 Principal design criteria for centrifuge

Unit design	Solid loading	≤100	kg TS/m ² /d
	Depth	≥3.0	m
	Removal efficiency	80-95	%
	Sludge concentration	20	%
Energy requirement	Specific energy consumption	100-140	kWh/ton TS

3.3.13 Drying unit

In order to increase the dry solid content of the sludge up to 90%, the water content in the sludge from the centrifuge needs to be evaporated. The energy required for drying the sludge (Q_{drying}) can be calculated using Eq. 11.

$$Q_{drying} = M_{ws} \cdot W \cdot [(Cp_{water} \cdot \Delta T) + \Delta H_{vap}] + [M_{ws} \cdot (1 - W)] \cdot Cp_{sludge} \cdot \Delta T \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

In which,

- M_{ws} : Mass of wet sludge after dewatering [kg]
- W : Water fraction [%]
- Cp_{water} : Heat capacity of the water [kJ/kg/°C]
- Cp_{sludge} : Heat capacity of the sludge [kJ/kg/°C]

ΔT : Temperature difference between initial and target temperatures [°C]
 ΔH_{vap} : Latent heat of water vaporization [kJ/kg]

Table 16 summarizes the design values for the calculation (Kim and Parker, 2008). With regards to the different sludge inputs, the heat capacity for each sludge would certainly be different. Literature values were used for the calculation (Ahn et al., 2009; Kim and Parker, 2008; Manjunatha et al., 2020), and the heat capacity of mixed-dried sludge was calculated based on the mass proportion of each sludge type.

Table 16 Principal design criteria for drying unit

Unit design	Target temperature	105	°C
	Heat capacity of water	4.18	kJ/kg/°C
	Heat capacity of sludge	1.70-1.95	kJ/kg/°C
	Latent heat of water vaporization	2090	kJ/kg

3.3.14 Pelletizing

Pelletizing is the process of creating small, dry and compact pellets from dried sludge, using a pellet mill (Bülher group, 2024). Pellet production can be attained through batch process, when the input quantity is large enough to run the pellet mill efficiently. In the analysis, a typical pellet mill running at 320 kW that can generate up to 50 t/h of pellets (Bülher group, 2024) was considered.

3.3.15 Composting

A composting facility should consist of various infrastructures designed to facilitate the composting process efficiently and in accordance with environmental regulations. Key infrastructures in a composting facility include: reception area (for incoming sludge and bulking material), pre-processing area (for pretreatment of sludge or bulking material), active composting area (for the actual composting process), storage areas for finished compost (before distribution or sale), leachate and stormwater management systems (to prevent runoff and potential environmental impacts), and buffer zones (to help control odours and as a barrier between the facility and neighbouring properties)⁸. Table 17 summarizes the design criteria used in the design of the composting unit (Johannessen et al., 2020). Eq. 12 was used to calculate the area requirement for the composting unit. A pile height of 2 meter and 28-day of composting period were adopted.

Table 17 Principal design criteria for the composting unit

Initial condition	%TS input	20	%
	Initial temperature after drying	15	°C
Composting reactor	Composting time	15-30	days
	Pile temperature	55-70	°C
	Height	1-3	m
Energy requirement	Specific energy consumption	5-10	kWh/ton

$$A = \frac{1.1 \times (V_{ST} - V_{BT})}{H} \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

⁸ <https://octopus-training.solidarites.org/courses/biosolids/>

In which,

- A : Pad area for the aerated static pile [m²]
- V_{ST} : Total sludge volume in T-days [m³]
- V_{BT} : Total bulking agent volume in T-days [m³]
- H : Height of the compost pile [m]

3.3.16 Pyrolysis

The pyrolysis process thermally converts organic matter in the absence of oxygen to produce bio-oil, pyrolysis gasoline (py-gas) and biochar. Different operating conditions (temperature and oxygen content) of the process can lead to different fractions of each product. In this study, dried digested sludge (at 90% TS) and garden waste (pre shredded) are used as input materials. Fraction of products detailed in Table 18 were extracted from (Kim and Parker, 2008) for digested sludge pyrolyzed at 500°C. Specific parameters for different stages of the pyrolysis process are also presented in Table 18. Energy requirement for pyrolysis process was split into the energy needed to heat up the dried sludge to target temperature and the energy needed to the reaction itself, including molecules reforming (Kim and Parker, 2008).

In terms of calorific values, average values from Kim and Parker (2008) for bio-oil and chars and from Cao and Pawłowski (2012) for py-gas were used. Py-gas is typically of lower quality than digester gas. It contains less methane, so its specific energy production was, thus, considered lower than methane (~1 kWh/kg lower).

Table 18 Principal design criteria for pyrolysis process

Initial condition	%TS input	90	%
	Initial temperature after drying	105	degree C
Reaction	Target temperature	500	degree C
	Energy consumed during the reaction	300	kJ/kg
Products	Py-gas fraction	21	%
	Py-gas calorific value	18.1	MJ/kg gas
	Bio-oil fraction	26	wt.%
	Bio-oil calorific value	37	MJ/kg-oil
	Biochar fraction	53	%
	Biochar calorific value	10	MJ/kg-TS

3.3.17 Combined Heat and Power (CHP) production

From the collected gas, CHP process utilizes the cogeneration principle to valorise heat generated from electricity production to generate both electricity and heat in an efficient way. Table 19 summarizes the design criteria for the CHP design.

Table 19 Principal design criteria for CHP design

Input fuel	%CH ₄ in biogas	65	%
	Specific energy form methane	9.3	kWh/Nm ³
	py-gas specific energy value	5	kWh/kg gas
Efficiency	typical electricity fraction	37%	
	typical heat fraction	48%	
	overall CHP efficiency	85%	

The CHP considered in the case study uses a gas engine to convert methane from AD and UASB, and py-gas from pyrolysis, into heat (~37%) and electricity (~48%) (Johannessen et al., 2020). The overall CHP efficiency process of 85% was considered (Cano et al., 2014). The biogas produced from AD and UASB was assumed to contain ~65% of methane (Ødegaard, 2012) with specific energy value of ~6.2 kWh/kg (Vidnes, 2014), whereas py-gas from pyrolysis is less pure and its specific energy value is only at ~5 kWh/kg py-gas (Cao and Pawłowski, 2012). The combustion process of the gas is not 100% efficient and some combustion residues and particulate matter are drawn through the exhaust gas filter. However, such an emission to the air is not part of the study.

3.4 Water smartness and sustainability assessment

The alternative processes should be assessed with a more holistic perspective than merely technical. In B-Water Smart a water smartness assessment framework has been developed as part of work package 6 (WP6). This framework is suited for assessment at the systemic level. In discussion with the WP6-lead, it was decided to use a framework that has been developed for the solution level. This assessment scale could be provided by the water smartness and sustainability (WS&S) assessment framework developed in the H2020 project WIDER UPTAKE (Helness et al., 2024b).

3.4.1 The concept, purpose, and structure of the water smartness framework

The WS&S framework allows one to assess how water-smart a solution is, and how it contributes towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This is done by comparing the properties the properties of the solution(s) under assessment with the properties of water smartness and sustainability as described by the vision of a water-smart society by Water Europe and relevant UN Sustainable Development Goals, respectively.

The properties of water smartness discussed in the Water Europe vision may be describes as follows (Seglem and Helness, 2023):

- Value of and in water
- Water management
- Water scarcity
- Water pollution
- Circularity and resource efficiency
- Resilience

The WS&S framework defines contributing to sustainability as having acceptable performance in five (5) dimensions at the same time: social, environment, economy, governance, and technical performance, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Sustainability dimensions (Seglem and Helness, 2023)

A key concept of the WS&S framework is “symbiotic circular economy solutions” (SCES), which have been defined in the WIDER UTAKÉ project as a package comprised of:

- The partners and stakeholders that collaborate to implement the solution,
- the resources to be recovered and the technologies to accomplish this,
- the business models that give economic value in a circular economy value chain,
- and the products and their applications

To assess how water smart a SCES is and how it contributes to sustainability, indicators that provide a measure of the compliance with a set of 15 pre-defined water smartness and sustainability objectives are used in the WS&S framework.

The indicators used in an assessment are selected from a set of 77 pre-defined indicators, thus a certain level of flexibility is allowed to properly cover a wide range of different type of solutions.

3.4.2 Conducting the water smartness assessment

For a detailed presentation of the WS&S framework and its application, the reader is referred to (Helness et al., 2024b). Here a summary with the main points is presented.

An assessment should involve all stakeholders to the SCES(s) under assessment and should begin by defining the boundaries to have a clear assessment scope. In doing this the assessment team should also consider if the assessment is to include multiple scenarios of alternative future conditions and define the assessment time horizon, which may include intermediate time steps, e.g., short-term, medium-term, and long term.

Selection of indicators should be done in collaboration with involved stakeholders. Iteration with some adjustment is normal to adjust indicators according to data availability. However, indicators should initially be based on relevance without considering data availability and one should select indicators that cover all the different dimensions to have a balanced assessment.

Selected indicators should be quantified and weighted in collaboration with local stakeholders. It is recommended that the source of indicator values and any calculations or processing of input values to obtain the indicator value is documented. The weighting should be relative considering all the selected indicators in an assessment.

3.4.3 Comparison by the WS&S Index

Comparison of alternatives may be done by the Water Smartness and Sustainability Index (WS&S Index) (Helness et al., 2024a). The index compiles the normalized average objective scores that are derived from the average weighted indicator scores.

The index is presented as a sector plot showing the 15 objectives and a single overall value between 0 and 1, where 1 implies perfect water smartness and sustainability.

In a comparison of several alternative solutions, the most water smart and sustainable will be the one with the higher WS&S Index. However, due consideration should be taken to the score of individual objectives and if there is missing data, which may often be the case, especially in an initial assessment.

4 Results from the technical assessment

4.1 Overview of solid treatment alternatives and recovered products

Process flow summary for each alternative is reported in APPENDIX B – Mass and energy balance for biogas and solid line. The circles on process box refer to energy consumption (in red) and energy production (in green). Mark that the results for solid treatment and recovered products in this section are based on reject water treatment Option B, except for Alternative 0 that is based on Option A (see Figure 3 for comparison of the two reject water treatment options). Alternative 0 was viewed to be the least likely alternative by Bodø Municipality, but was assessed, nonetheless. The sludge input for Alternative 0 is small, thus, the resource recovery option for this particular alternative was excluded. A thorough comparison between the two reject water options based on Alternative 1, which is considered as the baseline alternative in the case study, is presented in Section 4.2. Table 20 provides an overview of the recovered solid products from each alternative.

Table 20 Overview of the recovered solid products from each alternative

Alternative	Compost from sludge (kg DS/d)	Compost food waste (kg DS/d)	Biopellet (kg DS/d)	Biochar (kg DS/d)	Bio-oil (kg/d)
Alt. 0	475	-	-	-	-
Alt. 1	11 422	-	-	-	-
Alt. 2	-	-	4 037	-	-
Alt. 3	-	-	-	6 060	2 973
Alt. 4	-	-	-	7 312	3 587
Alt. 5	1 498	10 011	-	-	-

Dewatered sludge to be composted was considered at 20% dry solid (DS) content, as recommended by Breitenbeck and Schellinger (2004) and can be either mixed with garden waste (Alternative 1) to give an even dryer mixture or unmixed (Alternative 0). In the compost production, the input sludge is spread in aerated piles, which requires about 7.5 kWh/ton DS (Johannessen et al., 2020) and leads to a compost mass reduction of 2% (Fernando-Foncillas et al., 2021).

Compost can be directly used as soil improvement and fertilizer as it is rich in organic matter and nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorus. Compost can also contain pollutants such as heavy metals or pathogens and its direct use on soil is regulated by an European (and Norwegian in Norway) directive which prevent the use of sewage sludge compost on soil in which fruit and vegetable crops are grown, except for fruit trees or on grassland or forage land that will be grazed by animals or harvested in the next three weeks (Cherrier et al., 2022). As seen in Table 20, Alternatives 1 and 5 produce a similar amount of compost in total, while Alternative 0 produces, as expected, the lowest amount of compost given the much lower solid input for this alternative. However, the value for Alternative 5 is split into two to reflect the separate compost production from the input sludge (municipal, septic, and fish sludge) and food waste. The compost product originated from food waste in Alternative 5 (~10 tons DS/day) can be exempted from the restriction stated by the abovementioned EU directive. More information about the use of sludge for agricultural purposes can be found in the final study report on support to the evaluation of the Sewage Sludge Directive (86/278/EEC)⁹. Alternative 0 produces chemical sludge that is not

⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31986L0278>

included in compost production but needs to be handled separately. The post treatment for the chemical sludge was not included in this case study analysis.

Alternative 2 has biopellet production as the product for the solid line treatment. The analysis estimates the potential of biopellet production ~4 tons DS/day. Biopellets are essentially compacted dry sludge and can be used as primary fuel for thermal process given that its heating value of about 18.5 MJ/kg (Cusidó and Soriano, 2011). Another possible application is to use biopellets directly as a soil fertilizer owing to their nutrient content. Biopellets would then be subject to the same restrictions regarding direct application on land as compost.

Biochar is a by-product from pyrolysis that contains most of the residual pollutants such as heavy metals, but also has a high content of nutrients and organic material. Biochar is a carbon rich material and can be used as soil amendment agent or incorporated as building materials. This alternative has the advantage of reducing the volume of sludge that needs disposal and immobilizing contaminants, preventing them to leach into the environment and protecting water quality. Bio-oil is, on the other hand, a by-product of the pyrolysis process and can be a valuable product for applications as renewable energy source for various process applications, specifically it could be directly reinjected as fuel for pyrolysis process, but this is not assessed in this study. Bio-oil is of lower quality and has lower energy density compared to conventional fossil fuel but can still be used as feedstock for refining after stabilization and upgrading.

As seen in Table 20, Alternatives 3 and 4 deals with biochar and bio-oil as the recovered products from pyrolysis from two different biogas production steps: anaerobic digestion (AD) and up flow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB), respectively. As seen from the table, Alternative 4 can potentially produce higher quantities of biochar and bio-oil compared to Alternative 3. This is because a solid separation step was included in the process line upstream of the UASB. Consequently, the quantity of solids as input for pyrolysis is higher in Alternative 4 than in Alternative 3.

4.2 Reject water treatment

4.2.1 Overview of the governing EU Directives

Given the context of the reject water treatment assessed in this case study, two EU Directives are considered relevant: Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (c.q., Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2018/1147) and Council Directive 91/271/EEC of 21 May 1991 concerning urban waste-water treatment (c.q., Revision of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive In “A European Green Deal”¹⁰). The two directives follow two different approaches in determining the regulated discharge limits: discharge standard and pollution load approaches, respectively.

In the (EU) 2018/1147 document, the emission levels associated with the best available techniques (BAT-AEL) for direct emissions to a water recipient are given in Table 21 below. As seen from the table, the values in mg/l are quite restrictive regarding the quality of the water discharged, but there is no restriction on the discharge effluent flow and, thus, no restriction on the total daily amount of pollutant discharged to the receiving water bodies. The Directive proposes ranges of concentrations and the determination of the values to be applied depends

¹⁰ [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/carriage/revision-of-the-urban-wastewater-treatment-directive-\(refit\)/report?sid=8101](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/carriage/revision-of-the-urban-wastewater-treatment-directive-(refit)/report?sid=8101)

on some specific treatment conditions encountered, e.g., temperature of the wastewater to be treated, chloride concentration.

Table 21 Discharge limit according to the Industrial Wastewater Directive for direct emission to a water recipient (EU Commission, 2018)

Effluent parameter	Concentration [mg/L]
TSS	5–60
COD ¹¹	30–300
Tot-N ¹²	10-60
Tot-P	1-3

On the other hand, the Urban Wastewater Directive follows the pollutant load approach with treatment standards determined by the size of the discharge measured in person equivalents (p.e) and the condition of the recipient. According to the revision of the Urban Wastewater Directive the obligation to set up urban wastewater collecting systems would be extended to all agglomerations with 1000 inhabitants or more, compared to 2000 inhabitants currently implemented (Halleux, 2024). In addition, The EU Council and Parliament extended the obligation to apply secondary treatment (i.e., the removal of biodegradable organic matter) to urban wastewater before it is discharged into the environment to all agglomerations of 1000 p.e or more by 2035. For larger agglomerations removal of nutrients and selected micropollutants will also be required. These standards are normally required for discharges > 150000 p.e., but if the recipient is vulnerable, they will also apply for discharges > 10000 p.e. It is therefore of interest to assess what number of p.e the reject water discharge will correspond to.

Table 22 gives the daily amount per p.e. (Johannessen et al., 2020) in mg/d of the different pollutants assessed in this study (SS, COD, BOD₅, Tot-N and Tot-P) and the daily p.e. corresponding to reject water quality before treatment in Alternatives 0 and 1.

Table 22 Daily amount per p.e. (Johannessen et al., 2020)

Component	Amount per p.e. (mg/p.e./d)	Amount p.e. (p.e./d) in Alt.0	Amount p.e. (p.e./d) in Alt.1
SS	70	877	6630
COD	120	545	3481
BOD ₅	60	430	2689
Tot-N	12	1421	10053
Tot-P	1.8	2080	24660

The number of p.e. are above 1000 for Tot-N and Tot-P in Alternative 0 and for every component in Alternative 1, but still below 25000 p.e. At least secondary treatment would therefore probably be required if the UWWTD was to be applied. However, the Industry Directive specifies removal

¹¹ The upper part of the interval may not apply in the following cases: — When the treatment efficiency is $\geq 95\%$ as a rolling annual average and the supplied waste has the following characteristics: TOC > 2 g/l (or COD > 6 g/l) which daily average and a high proportion of difficult-to-degrade organic compounds (i.e., which are difficult to break down biologically) or — at high chloride concentrations (e.g., over 5 g/l in the added waste)

¹² The BAT-AEL value may not apply when the temperature of the wastewater is low (e.g., below 12 °C). The BAT-AEL value may not apply to high chloride concentrations (e.g., over 10 g/l in the added waste). The BAT-AEL value only applies when biological treatment of wastewater is used.

of nutrients without considering the size of the discharge and this will be deciding for the required treatment.

4.2.2 Overview of the reject water treatment options

Table 1 depicts the two options for reject water treatment, Options A and B, which have been assessed and assigned to the different alternatives in the case study. This section compares the reject water treatment options based on Alternative 1 to provide an overview of the technical and economic consequences they pose. For the sake of clarity, Table 23 highlights the solid and the reject water treatment lines used in the comparison. The flow schemes of reject water treatment options are presented in Figure 3.

Table 23 Summary of the reject water treatment options

Alternative	Solid line	Reject water treatment line
Alt.1_(A)	THP-AD-composting	Denitrifying MBBR with chemicals addition for phosphorous removal
Alt.1_(B)	THP-AD-composting	MBBR (organic removal) with Struvite – Anammox

Short summary of each option:

Alt.1_(A) : The technology for reject water treatment is applied on the reject water produced by Alternative 1. The reject water treatment involves pre- and post-sedimentation tanks for a MBBR process with nitrogen removal. The C/N ratio in the reject water (3,5) is lower than needed for the required N-removal (should be equal or higher than 4 g BOF₅/g NO₃-N_{equiv, removed} (Johannessen et al., 2020). A post denitrification process with addition of external C-source has therefore been assumed. This is a simplification compared to a probable process solution, but gives a conservative design compared to a process with combined pre- and post-denitrification where the influent organic matter provides some of the carbon source for denitrification. Chemical addition for phosphorous removal is considered for the MBBR effluent to meet the effluent criteria. This solution produces chemical sludge in the post-sedimentation tank, which needs to be further handled separately before disposal. Chemical sludge disposal is beyond the boundaries of this study.

Alt.1_(B) : The technology for reject water treatment is applied on the reject water produced by Alternative 1. The reject water treatment line involves pre- and post- sedimentation tanks for the MBBR unit, and another sedimentation tank after the anammox unit. The MBBR is designed exclusively for BOD₅ removal. The struvite process is integrated after the post-sedimentation tank of MBBR, providing adequate conditions for phosphorous removal through formation of struvite crystals, followed by anammox process for nitrogen removal.

4.2.3 Comparison between Options A and B

4.2.3.1 Effluent quality

Table 24 summarize the effluent water quality from Options A and B applied to Alternative 1 and subjected to the Directive 2010/75/EU (EU Commission, 2018). The detailed mass balance analyses for Alternative 1 applying Options A and B are given in Appendices C.2 Alternatives 1 Option , C.3 Alternatives 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

As seen in Table 24, the treated reject water from Option A fulfils the discharge limit of the regulated parameters stated in Directive 2010/75/EU (EU Commission, 2018) except for suspended solids (SS). Mark that a separation efficiency of 85% for SS was applied in the analysis. Given that Option A involves addition of coagulant/flocculant aids, a higher separation efficiency can be expected in the expense of production of chemical sludge that requires further handling. On the other hand, the effluent from Option B shows compliance for the organic and particulate discharge limits but indicates higher nutrient concentrations (N and P) than the values dictated by the regulation. The mass balance analysis indicates predominantly higher ammonium and phosphate that contribute to the total nutrient concentrations. Non-compliances shown by Options A and B do not render the technological solutions considered in this case study inappropriate, but rather that the simplified designs are suboptimal. Given that some of the data in the analysis came from literature values, it is highly advised to conduct a separate study with firmer baseline data.

Table 24 Effluent quality comparison between Options A and B (in mg/L) vs. Directive 2010/75/EU

	Unit	Alt.1_(A)	Alt.1_(B)	Discharge limit
Quantity	m ³ /d	52.35	66.54	-
SS	mg/L	377.54	41.91	5-60
COD	mg/L	176.60	45.63	30-300
Tot-N	mg/L	6.00	101.48	10-60
Tot-P	mg/L	0.48	4.37	1-3

The analysis shows that Option B would potentially release less organic and particulate pollutants to the environment compared to those of Option A, except for Tot-P and Tot-N as discussed also in the preceding paragraph. However, Option A requires almost 2 kg of coagulant/flocculant chemicals per day to precipitate the phosphorous, which leads to production of chemical sludge that required further handling. Moreover, Option B recovers phosphorous thanks to the struvite process that produces a nutrient based crystal that can be potentially sold or used as fertilizer.

In conclusion, both options are technically feasible and can comply with future stringent regulations. However, owing to less chemical requirements and the potential valuable product recovered, Option B would be a better recommendation to pursue.

4.2.3.2 Energy and footprint for the treatment units

Figure 6 compares the area, volume and power requirements for Options A and B of the reject water treatment process. As seen in the figure, Option B clearly demands less treatment footprints than Option A. The largest discrepancy belongs to the area and volume requirement for complete nitrogen removal by MBBR, given that the MBBR in Option B is dedicated solely for organic removal. As mentioned, the design of the nitrogen removal in Option A is conservative, however, in comparison the additional reactors for struvite and anammox process in Option B do not significantly contribute to the total required footprints and can be designed as a compact system.

Aeration takes up the largest part of energy consumption by an MBBR system. Consequently, the energy consumption in Option A is slightly higher than that of Option B, even after the aeration for partial nitrification prior to anammox process in Option B is included (~10% higher). Indeed, the energy requirements for denitrifying MBBR of typically ~0.2-0.3 kWh/m³

(Johannessen et al., 2020) are somewhat higher than the combined MBBR for organic removal, struvite and anammox option of $\sim 0.1-0.2$ kWh/m³ (Ghimire et al., 2021), favouring Option B to be the more energy efficient out of the two options. Option B, though, requires an inflow of seawater into the struvite process. The seawater involves pretreatment (e.g., pre-screening) and pumping energy. These elements would contribute to a higher energy requirement for Option B but were excluded from the analysis and should affect the technical feasibility of Option B. Aeration takes up the largest part of energy consumption by an MBBR system. Consequently, the energy consumption in Option A is slightly higher than that of Option B, even after that the aeration for partial nitrification prior to anammox process in Option B is included ($\sim 10\%$ higher). Indeed, the energy requirements for denitrifying MBBR of typically $\sim 0.2-0.3$ kWh/m³ (Johannessen et al., 2020) are somewhat higher than the combined MBBR for organic removal, struvite and anammox option of $\sim 0.1-0.2$ kWh/m³ (Ghimire et al., 2021), favouring Option B to be the more energy efficient out of the two options. Option B, though, requires an inflow of seawater into the struvite process. The seawater involves pretreatment (e.g., pre-screening) and pumping energy. These two elements would contribute to a higher energy requirement for Option B, but were excluded from the analysis and should not pose threats to the technical feasibility of Option B.

Figure 6 Comparison of reject water Options A and B

4.2.4 Overall comparison of effluent quality of each alternative

Table 25 presents summary of the reject water quality for the different alternatives based on reject water treatment Option B subjected to the Directive 2010/75/EU (EU Commission, 2018). The complete mass balance analyses for each alternative are reported in APPENDIX C – Mass and energy balance for reject water line.

As seen in Table 25, the reject water quality from Alternative 0 complies with the Industrial Wastewater Directive (Directive 2010/75/EU), except for the SS parameter. On the other hand, the other ‘recovery’ alternatives (Alternatives 1-5) do not show effluent SS to be a problem, but rather the nutrient parameters are rather higher than the regulation values, especially phosphorus. Of a particular interest, Alternative 4 that employs UASB has a potential to conform with the nitrogen requirement compared to the other recovery alternatives. Alternative 4 leads to discharged water with lower SS, Tot-N and Tot-P content than those of the other alternatives.

The fact that the UASB alternative involves an extra solid separation unit prior to the biogas production, this leads to a much lower solid loading for the downstream process, including the reject water treatment.

Table 25 Effluent quality summary for the different alternatives (in mg/L) vs. Directive 2010/75/EU

	Unit	Alt.0	Alt.1	Alt.2	Alt.3	Alt.4	Alt.5	Discharge limit
Quantity	(m ³ /d)	13.49	66.54	66.54	66.54	52.47	63.06	-
SS	mg/L	258.37	41.91	41.91	41.91	26.21	56.79	5-60
COD	mg/L	120.46	45.63	29.53	29.77	40.06	29.61	30-300
Tot-N	mg/L	6.00	101.48	101.48	101.48	45.16	92.29	10-60
Tot-P	mg/L	0.56	4.37	4.37	4.37	4.21	3.94	1-3

As examined in the preceding section, the non-conformity underlines the need for fine tuning of the design parameter and does not imply the technology is inappropriate. It is important to note that in the case of discharge permit following the industrial waste water directive report (EU Commission, 2018), additional chemical can be required to meet the discharge limit of suspended solid and phosphorus set in Table 21.

4.3 Overall comparison of process dimensioning

The complete information about the dimension of each unit operation and process is presented in APPENDIX B – Mass and energy balance for biogas and solid line and APPENDIX C – Mass and energy balance for reject water line.

Figure 7 shows the overall footprint requirements of the different alternatives shown as stacked bars reflecting the different stages involved. As seen from the figure, the transformation process from sludge to product is the one that requires most space considering the compost alternatives (Alternatives 1 and 5). The shredder machine¹³ alone has a negligible footprint, but the composting infrastructure should include a reception area (for incoming sludge and bulking material), pre-processing area (for pretreatment of sludge or bulking material), active composting area (for the actual composting process), and storage areas for finished compost (before distribution or sale). In addition to that, a leachate and stormwater management system to prevent runoff and potential environmental impacts, and buffer zones to help control odours and as a barrier between the facility and neighbouring properties will come as an addition. The calculated area requirement for composting unit in this study is therefore underestimated. The pyrolysis process takes up a larger area requirement than that of pelletizing. This is based on one typical commercial pyrolysis unit¹⁴. Half of required area for pelletizing (e.g., Bülher group, 2024) should be dedicated for space for drying (Stowell, 2018). Meanwhile a half of required area for pelletizing (e.g., Bülher group, 2024) should be dedicated for space for drying (Stowell, 2018).

Regarding solid treatment stage, Alternatives 1-3, and 5 with AD exhibit a higher footprint requirement than Alternative 4 with UASB. As seen in Figure 7, the needed area for Alternative 4 represents roughly half of the other alternatives. There is of course a trade-off for this advantage. Alternative 4 requires a pretreatment (i.e., a centrifuge) prior to the UASB unit that implies extra investment and operational expenses.

¹³ [stq-new.pdf \(shred-tech.com\)](https://stq-new.pdf(shred-tech.com))

¹⁴ <https://www.bestongroup.net/waste-tyre-rubber-oil-sludge-prolysis-plant-for-sale>

On the other hand, reject water treatment and solid pretreatment with the different mixing units have negligible footprint in comparison to the solid treatment and the product transformation stages. Note that every surface area presented here was calculated based on the allowable surface loading (Johannessen et al., 2020) and a predetermined tank depth, not on the exact reactor size of the process itself in addition to its surrounding area. It can be expected that by including the surrounding area (i.e., for real operation of the processes), Alternative 5 that is composed of two separate lines, would have a larger footprint. (Johannessen et al., 2020) and a predetermined tank depth, not on the exact reactor size of the process itself in addition to its surrounding area. It can be expected that by including the surrounding area (i.e., for real operation of the processes), Alternative 5 that is composed of two separate lines, should produce a much larger footprint.

Figure 7 Footprint of the different alternatives

Mark that Alternative 0 with sludge input only from Bodø shows the least area requirement simply owing to lesser input materials to handle and reject water to treat. Even though this alternative was the starting point of the whole discussion of energy recovery from solid wastes in Bodø Municipality, this option may prove economically unattractive given that the amounts of biogas and compost are small compared to Alternative 1 with sludge from the whole Salten area.

Figure 8 Volume requirement of the different alternatives

Figure 8 shows the required volume for different alternatives. In contrast to the area requirement, the volume requirement for solid treatment stage makes up the largest proportion of the total volume followed by the product transformation and reject water treatment, respectively. This holds true for Alternatives 0-3 and 5, but not for Alternative 4, because the volume requirement depends on the type of technology. The UASB unit in Alternative 4 can potentially offer lower volume requirement compared to the AD process, with some trade-offs discussed in the preceding paragraph. The required volumes for reject water and pre-treatment are miniscule compared to the other two stages. It can be noted that reject water treatment necessitates a slightly larger volume for Alternative 5 because, in the analysis, the volume of treated reject water (~10 m³/d) is reinjected at the beginning of the process to be mixed with the food waste to get the appropriate solid fraction for treatment. Every volume is calculated based on the volume of water handled.

The results presented so far can provide a background for technical feasibility assessment of the proposed alternatives for the decision makers. As discussed, both solid and reject water alternatives can comply with the regulation and potentially generate economically valuable products. It is not straightforward to make direct inferences on the economic feasibility of these alternatives. However, this is included in Chapter 5 discussing the water smartness and sustainability of the different alternatives.

4.4 Energy balance

In the case study, energy requirement and production values were calculated based on values from the literature for each process separated into electricity or heat and excluding additional operational energy requirements. Specific values of energy requirement and production for each alternative can be found in APPENDIX B – Mass and energy balance for biogas and solid line and APPENDIX C – Mass and energy balance for reject water line. In both appendices, the energy requirement and production from each the process are tagged with red and green circles, respectively.

Figure 9 depicts the detailed comparison of the net energy balance for each alternative considered in the case study.

Figure 9 Net power demand and production from the different treatment processes

4.4.1 Energy demand

In the analysis, the net energy demand for different parts in the process scheme is divided between the demand in electricity and heat. The net power demand represents the gross power needed to run the specific process.

Electricity is consumed to run the main components of the treatment scheme such as mixing units¹⁵, food shredder¹⁶, dewatering and centrifuge (Johannessen et al., 2020), garden waste shredder¹⁷, etc. Note that pumps, lights, or any other appliances that may consume electricity have not been included in the analysis. Pyrolysis energy demand is calculated using direct electricity (electric heating or fluidized bed reactor for example) for heating the feedstock to the target temperature and for the reaction itself (Kim and Parker, 2008), as it is assumed that there is no available heat at this temperature (105-500°C). Moreover, the potential heat recovery from combustion processes were excluded from the study.

The heat demand for Alternatives 0, 1, and 5 is exclusively linked to the THP unit in order to create the feeding steam at 170°C in each alternative. For Alternatives 2, 3, and 4, additional heat is needed to dry the dewatered sludge before pyrolysis process. In this regard, drying is done at relatively low temperature (105°C) and, thus, heat could be directly reused from another

¹⁵ <https://sodimate.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/SODIMATE-MBV-EN.pdf>

¹⁶ <https://www.jwce.com/products/4-shred-2/>

¹⁷ <https://shred-tech.com/shred-tech-stq-50-industrial-shredder/>

process that produces excess heat (e.g., pyrolysis or CHP). However, heat recovery from energy production unit was outside the boundaries of this study.

4.4.2 Energy production

Direct energy production comes from the CHP unit, providing both electricity and heat by combining heat and power production from the methane gas coming out of the AD/UASB (see APPENDIX B – Mass and energy balance for biogas and solid line for more details). For Alternatives 3 and 4, the py-gas generated from the pyrolysis process is also included into the CHP unit, thus, the amount of heat and electricity generated from these alternatives are significantly higher than the others. The bio-oil potential reflects the raw potential power of the bio-oil produced during the considered pyrolysis reaction (Ahn et al., 2009) without any conversion factor. The actual energy recovery potential from bio-oil is lower and its exact value depends on the type of downstream process it will be used for. For example, direct reuse as feed for the thermic combustion process or other indirect applications. If the indirect applications are aimed, the bio-oil requires upgrading to produce high quality biofuels (Gunawan et al., 2013). Such a discussion is beyond the scope of this case study, but as stated above, bio-oil production is considered a contributing factor to the overall energy production.

4.4.3 Summary of energy balance

The energy demand and production from different process unit in each alternative is summarize in Figure 10. As seen in the figure, Alternative 0 is really energy friendly owing to the small quantity of waste to be treated. Alternatives 1 and 2 produce the same quantity of electricity and heat from the CHP unit. The difference with energy production from Alternative 3 is due to the py-gas that is also burned in CHP. The high heat demand in Alternative 2 is associated with the required drying of sludge before pelletizing, and similarly for pyrolysis in Alternatives 3 and 4. As discussed in the preceding section, for Alternative 4 there is a need for a dedicated centrifuge unit before the UASB and, thus, more sludge is directly sent to drying leading to lower heat production in UASB, higher drying demand and thus, larger amount of pyrolysis products. Alternative 5 presents identical results as Alternative 1 in terms of energy balance owing to the similar processes involved in the two alternatives. Note that the differences lie on the footprints for these two alternatives as discussed in Section 4.3.

Figure 10 Net energy balance for the different alternatives

The net power generation (green bar) in Figure 10 shows the cumulation of excess power generated by each alternative, including the energy generation from bio-oil (blue bar). One can observe that, in fact, Alternative 4 leads to a negative power production if the bio-oil potential is excluded since the potential energy recovery from this alternative solely comes from the bio-oil production. This differentiation is done as a precaution owing to the discussion in the preceding section that informs the energy recovery potential from bio-oil is lower and its exact value depends on the type of downstream process it will be used for and requires upgrading to produce high quality biofuels. Hence, for Alternative 4 the potential energy recovery comes exclusively in the form of bio-oil production.

The term “net positive” in the context of a wastewater treatment facility signifies a paradigm shift. Instead of merely treating and disposing of wastewater, the wastewater treatment plants are designed to induce beneficial impacts on the environment. With regard to the provisional political agreement on a proposal to review the Revision of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (Halleux, 2024), it has been agreed that the urban wastewater treatment sector could significantly reduce GHG emissions and help the EU achieve its climate neutrality objective. In the abovementioned document, European parliament introduce an energy neutrality target, proposing that by 2045 urban wastewater treatment plants will have to produce energy from renewable sources, based on regular energy audits, with progressive intermediate targets.

However, to conclude about a net positive treatment facility for one of the alternatives, the overall efficiency of energy conversion processes and sludge transport (pipes, pumps, etc.) must be considered. It is too premature to draw conclusions about the net positivity of the alternatives, but the exercise done in the case study has shown the potential of a net energy positive of sludge treatment in Bodø Municipality and Salten area. Every alternative produces a positive net energy than the net power demand for running the different treatment processes, as shown in Figure 10. Hence, there is a good indication of the potential net positive energy balance from the different alternatives.

5 Water smartness and sustainability assessment

The WS&S assessment was conducted as a workshop in Bodø (13th-14th March 2024) with follow-up activities by SINTEF.

Participants at the workshop were from Bodø municipality and Iris, the company that currently handles sludge from Bodø and other solid waste. Not all participants could attend both days.

The workshop followed the procedure for a WS&S assessment starting with selection of relevant indicators by the local stakeholders, thereafter the time was devoted to discussing the weight of the different indicators and initial quantification where possible. In the cases where an indicator was selected as relevant, but it was not possible to set a value, it was discussed how such values could be obtained. For some indicators, quantification was then done by SINTEF based on either the technical part of the assessment or based on publicly available data. This will be discussed further below.

At the workshop, alternatives 0 through 4 were discussed. Later SINTEF added also Alternative 5, which is equal to Alternative 1, but with two separate lines for wastewater sludge and food waste, respectively. The quantification of the indicators for this alternative has been based on the stakeholder input for Alternative 1, adjusted as deemed appropriate considering separate treatment of wastewater sludge and food waste. This will be discussed further below.

The overall evaluation of the assessment is that the data represent only an initial level of a WS&S assessment. There are several indicators that could not be quantified due to lack of available data and where the stakeholders did not feel confident to provide even a rough estimate. There are also several indicators where the stakeholders could only provide a relative ranking of the alternatives instead of the actual values for the indicators. Further there are some indicators where proxy-indicators for which data could be obtained, were used instead of the indicators specified in the framework for which numerical data could not be obtained. These limitations are not uncommon in the initial round of an assessment, which then has a high level of uncertainty that the user should be aware of. However, the assessment can and should be improved by further iterations where more indicators are quantified, and the accuracy of the data is improved.

5.1 Selection, weighting, and quantification of indicators

The selection, weighting, and quantification of indicators at the workshop was done per dimension after a short introduction of each by SINTEF. Details regarding the different indicators are provided below.

5.1.1 Social dimension

The objectives in the social dimension concern:

- Social benefits from wastewater management (S1)
- Human well-being from recovered resources (S2)
- Knowledge and acceptance of recovered resources and products of such (S3)

Selection of indicators was done from a pre-defined list. For the social dimension 8 out of 12 indicators were selected. The indicators that were not selected would only be relevant in a case including a wastewater treatment plant. The selected indicators were given average or high weight and quantified by the local stakeholders at the workshop.

In some cases, the quantification of the indicators was not according to the same scale as used in the framework, e.g., a %-value could be provided by the stakeholders, but the framework indicator is based on a 1-5 Likert scale. In such cases, the data were processed by range normalization to the scale used in the framework. If a maximum and minimum value, as required for range normalization, could not be specified for the data provided, the range of the provided data was used for the normalization. This procedure was also followed for the other dimensions.

5.1.2 Environmental dimension

For environmental aspects, the objectives are related to:

- Environmental impacts (En1)
- Preservation of nature (En2)
- Climate change mitigation (En3)

For the environmental dimension 13 out of 16 indicators were selected as relevant by the local stakeholders. However, at the workshop data could only be provided to give an estimate on the effect on ecosystem health. After the workshop estimates for direct discharges to water and level of carbon footprint were obtained based on the technical assessment.

With respect to discharges to water (indicator En 1.2.1) the sum of yearly discharges of total COD, total nitrogen and total phosphorus given in kg/year) were used.

The level of carbon footprint was based on the specific net energy estimated as the net energy (produced from biogas and bio-oil – consumed in the process) divided by the reject water flow. The estimates were normalized to a 1-5 Likert scale as discussed above.

5.1.3 Economic dimension

In the economic dimension the objectives are related to

- Direct economic value in the value chain of the solution (Ec1)
- Additional economic benefits to parties involved (Ec2)
- Additional economic benefits to society (Ec3)

For the economic dimension all the 10 indicators were selected as relevant by the local stakeholders.

Economic feasibility often refers to whether a project or investment is financially viable and can generate a positive return. In the WS&S farmwork indicators for this that are suited for private companies and public entities have been included. However, at the time of the workshop, the assessments being done by Iris and Bodø municipality in this respect were still at a too early stage to provide such estimates. Proxy indicators for total cost were therefore used and based on the volume and area of the processes required for the different alternatives. These properties will be related to investment costs and operating costs, where volume is related to investment cost and area is related to operation costs, with higher values giving higher costs.

A rough estimate for the level total annual cost (indicator Ec 2.1.3) was based on the sum of total process volume and footprint for each alternative as found in the technical assessment normalized to a 1-5 Likert scale to provide an initial estimated for ranking of the alternatives. Regarding the volume requirement, this reflects the construction, equipment, and other physical utilities that need investment at the start of the construction of a facility. Many types of expenditure can contribute to the total operational costs. In general, the larger the area the larger

the cost of operation and maintenance will be. Hence, with utmost precautions, Figures 11 and 12 can indicate the magnitude of operational and investment costs for each alternative. It should be noted, however, that this approach does not consider that an investment will be depreciated over a period of years. Further differences between the footprint of alternatives due to required walkways and space around equipment was not considered.

Estimates for the value provided by the products derived from the recovered resource have also been estimated based on the technical assessment and should be verified and updated when the business models for the solution have been further developed by the local stakeholders. The economic value of products derived from recovered resources (indicator Ec 1.1.2) have been estimated based on openly available sources, which are provided below:

- Compost: 650 NOK/m³ ¹⁸
- Bio-oil: 24.1 NOK/L¹⁹
- Biopellets:
 - 16.6 MJ/kg for sludge pellets, based on 19.5 MJ/kg for wood (Telmo and Lousada, 2011)
 - 7681 NOK/ton sludge pellets, based on 9024 NOK/ton for wood pellets²⁰
- Biochar: 8000 NOK/ton (Prestvik and Stine Lilleby, 2021)

To estimate the value provided in the different alternatives, the quantity for a period of one year as determined in the technical assessment has been used as the basis.

5.1.4 Governance dimension

In the governance dimension, the objectives are related to:

- Compliance to regulatory objectives (G1)
- Contribution towards Integrated Water Management (G2)
- Participation of stakeholders (G3)

For the governance dimension all 9 indicators were selected as relevant by the local stakeholders.

At the workshop in Bodø (13-14 March 2024), the local stakeholders quantified the indicators for each of the alternatives. As for the social indicators, the provided input was given as an initial estimate to rank the alternatives. All the indicators in the governance dimension have a 1-5 Likert scale. Input data concerning stakeholder participation, which was provided as an estimated number of events, was range normalized to this scale as described above for the social dimension.

5.1.5 Technical performance

In the technical dimension the objectives related to:

- Performance targets of the wastewater utilities (Tp1)
- Targets for quality and quantity of recovered resources and products of these (Tp2)
- Circularity of resources (Tp3).

¹⁸ <https://www.ivarryfylke.no/aktuelt/arets-ivar-kompost-er-klar>

¹⁹ <https://drivenergi.no/privat/produkter-og-priser/>

²⁰ <https://www.biopellets.no/butikk/trepellets/biowood-basic.html>

For technical performance 6 out of 10 indicators were selected as relevant by the local stakeholders. At the workshop, no quantification of the indicators was done by the local stakeholders for the same reasons related to the stage of the assessment process at Iris and Bodø municipality as discussed above.

The technical assessment, however, provided a basis for estimation of the degree of circularity for selected compounds. The Material Circularity Index (indicator Tp3.1.1) was therefore estimated for phosphorus and nitrogen based on the quantities in the recovered struvite compared to the inlet material for Alternatives 2, 3, and 4, and the quantities in the recovered struvite and compost for Alternatives 1 and 5.

5.2 WS&S Index for the different alternatives

The WS&S assessment based on the WS&S Index provides an overall score of water smartness and sustainability and more detailed results on the objective level.

5.2.1 Overall score

The overall WS&S Index for each of the six alternatives (Alternatives 0 – 5) is shown in Figure 11. When interpreting the scores, one should consider the level of uncertainty due to limitations in the source data as discussed in the previous section. However, the results confirm the results from the technical assessment with respect to the required amounts of sludge as seen when comparing Alternative 0 to the other alternatives.

Further the results indicate that aiming for other products than compost in addition to biogas is favourable. However, one should also here consider the uncertainties related to the value chains for the products, e.g., is there an established value chain with all required partners in place for the product or will there be a need to develop this aspect to realize the potential economic value.

Figure 11 Overall water smartness and sustainability score for the different alternatives

Comparing Alternative 1 and Alternative 5, the results indicate that having separate lines for wastewater sludge and food waste will be favourable. In the assessment this is due to a more favourable score with respect to risk and compliance with regulations. However, the cost aspect of having two separate process lines has not been fully captured using the sum of volume and footprint as a proxy for total cost because the volumes and areas calculated for the solution with two separate lines only accounts for the process equipment and are therefore underestimated. The cost difference will therefore probably be higher than accounted for here.

Overall, the results indicate that Alternative 4 will be the preferred solution. This is mainly due to a combination of having valuable products (biogas, bio-oil and biochar) and saving volume and presumably investment costs by using an UASB instead of an anaerobic digester. The results are in line with what one would expect based on the comparisons of volume and footprint as well as the energy balance in the technical assessment. However, one should take this only as a preliminary conclusion that should be verified considering the uncertainties in the value chain for bio-oil and biochar and the level of accuracy in the technical evaluation.

5.2.2 Scores at the objective level

The WS&S assessment also provides results at the objective level as weighted objective scores normalized to a scale of 0 to 10 with 10 being the most favourable value. The objective scores are presented in a sector plot that is filled from the outside in. The sector plots for the different alternatives are presented in Figure 12 where the blue colour shows the score for each objective and the grey colour illustrated the remaining potential for improvement for each objective and where there is a lack of data to quantify the indicators and calculate the objective score.

For all alternatives one can see the limited data availability for the technical performance indicators resulting in the fully grey sectors for two of the three objectives concerning technical performance. To improve the assessment, data related to Performance targets of the wastewater utilities (Tp1) and Targets for quality and quantity of recovered resources and products of these (Tp2) will be required. Considering that the solution under assessment is for sludge management, especially objective-Tp2 will be relevant to assess further.

Data to quantify indicators related to Additional economic benefits to society (Ec3), are also lacking. Such data can best be provided by the local stakeholders when the planning process at Iris has progressed further, and an economic comparison of the alternatives can be included in the assessment.

The scores for the objectives in the environmental dimension consider the estimated total yearly discharges of the parameters regulated by the industrial effluent directive and the levels of ecosystem health and carbon footprint. Although data to quantify additional indicators is desired, a score for all objectives in the environmental dimension could be obtained. The difference between alternatives reflects the different properties of the solutions.

The scores for the social dimension were provided by the local stakeholders at the workshop. The main difference is between Alternative 0 and the other alternatives, which is related to the amount of sludge. There were also some differences in the scoring of risk which had a positive impact on the score for objective S2 in Alternative 5.

Quantification of the governance indicators were also provided by the stakeholders at the workshop. The effect of separating wastewater sludge from food waste can be seen in the score for objective G1, which is related to compliance with regulations, when comparing Alternative 1 and Alternative 5. The scores for the governance objectives for the other alternatives show the ranking of the alternatives given by the stakeholders.

Combined, the sector plots show clearly that data availability has been an issue at this initial assessment and confirms that one should consider the results preliminary, and that they should be verified before concluding as to which alternative will be the most water smart and sustainable.

Alt. 0: Only Bodø sludge; Compost; WS&S Index: 0,37

a)

Alt. 1: Salten sludge; Compost; WS&S Index: 0,42

b)

Alt. 2: Salten sludge; Dried pellets; WS&S Index: 0,54

c)

Alt. 3: Salten sludge; Biochar; WS&S Index: 0,63

d)

Alt. 4: Salten sludge; UASB+Biochar; WS&S Index: 0,73

e)

Alt. 5: Salten sludge; Two lines, Compost; WS&S Index: 0,49

f)

Figure 12 Sector plots of the WS&S Index for Alternatives 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, respectively

6 Conclusions and recommendations

Six alternatives (Alternatives 0-5) were assessed to evaluate the potential of biogas production from different sludge and solid waste streams from Bodø and the surrounding area in Salten. The technical assessment was extended to compare the water smartness and sustainability of the alternatives using the Water Smartness and Sustainability Index developed in the H2020 project WIDER UPTAKE, which is collaboration with B-Water Smart in the CIRSEAU cluster.

Conclusions from the technical assessment of the alternatives:

- Biogas recovered from digester was calculated for all alternatives, with its net energy production potential through CHP unit. Alternatives 3 and 4 include biogas generated through pyrolysis unit (py-gas). Alternative 4 had the most favourable net energy balance.
- Compost in cold climate countries can require additional energy for heating the compost pile to mesophilic condition during winter, which will affect the energy requirement of this solution. Further, the availability of sufficient agricultural land with crops that allow use of wastewater sludge for soil improvement close to the treatment plant must be assessed to define the viability of Alternatives 0, 1 and 5 that produce compost.
- Biopellets, biochar, and bio-oil from Alternatives 2, 3 and 4 are valuable products that can be sold on the market as fertilizer for the first two, or directly reused as fuel for different processes (biopellets or bio-oil). A specific study of the market opportunities is recommended to be carried out to assess this potential further.
- Alternative 3, with pyrolysis of the digestate from the anaerobic digester where biogas is produced has the most power production excess, closely followed by Alternative 4 that uses an UASB for biogas production.
- Alternative 4 with UASB for biogas production is the most compact alternative with lowest footprint compared to other alternatives using conventional anaerobic digestors. Considering the close relation between infrastructure size and cost, Alternative 4 may be the preferred solution from a cost perspective.
- For all alternatives, reject water treatment can be by a traditional end of pipe solution or, alternatively, be with implemented with recovery of struvite fertilizer. For both cases optimization of the design will be required to ensure compliance with the expected discharge standards.

The assessment of water smartness and sustainability confirms the need for more sludge than available in Bodø municipality and that aiming for other products than compost in addition to biogas is favourable. The results from the assessment show clearly that data availability has been an issue. One should therefore consider this as a preliminary assessment.

Overall, the results indicate that Alternative 4 will be the preferred solution. This is mainly due to a combination of having valuable products (biogas, biooil and biochar), and saving volume and presumably investment costs by using an UASB instead of an anaerobic digester. This is what one would expect based on the comparisons of volume and footprint as well as the energy balance in the technical assessment. However, as noted, one should take this only as a preliminary conclusion that should be verified considering the uncertainties in the value chain for biooil and biochar and the level of accuracy in the technical evaluation.

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APPENDIX A – Elemental balance for biogas production

Stoichiometric mass balance of the elements of an organic mixture follow the equation below (Moscoviz and Jimenez, 2021):

where:

$$a = 1 - 0.25 \cdot h - 0.5 \cdot o + 1.75 \cdot n - (Y_{X/S}/4.2) \cdot (2.6 + 0.65 \cdot h - 1.3 \cdot o - 1.95 \cdot n)$$

$$b = (1 - Y_{X/S}) \cdot (0.5 + 0.125 \cdot h - 0.25 \cdot o - 0.375 \cdot n)$$

$$c = 0.5 - 0.125 \cdot h + 0.25 \cdot o - 0.625 \cdot n - (Y_{X/S}/4.2) \cdot (1.1 + 0.275 \cdot h - 0.55 \cdot o - 0.825 \cdot n)$$

$$d = n - (Y_{X/S}/4.2) \cdot (0.8 + 0.2 \cdot h - 0.4 \cdot o - 0.6 \cdot n)$$

$$e = (Y_{X/S}/4.2) \cdot (4 + h - 2 \cdot o - 3 \cdot n)$$

and $Y_{X/S}$ is expressed in $\text{gCOD}_X/\text{gCOD}_{\text{consumed}}^{-1}$.

APPENDIX B – Mass and energy balance for biogas and solid line

B.1 Alternative 0

B.2 Alternative 1

B.3 Alternative 2

B.4 Alternative 3

B.5 Alternative 4

B.6 Alternative 5

APPENDIX C – Mass and energy balance for reject water line

C.1 Alternative 0

C.2 Alternatives 1 Option A

C.3 Alternatives 1, 2 and 3

C.3 Alternative 4

C.5 Alternative 5

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